

Comprehensive Assessment of Open Science Practices in Indoor Positioning: Open Data, Code and Material

Grigorios G. Anagnostopoulos, Paolo Barsocchi, Antonino Crivello, Cristiano Pendão, Ivo Silva, and Joaquín Torres-Sospedra

Abstract— Transparency and verifiability have long been regarded as cornerstones of the scientific ethos and practice. However, persistent reproducibility challenges across numerous disciplines have brought renewed attention to the imperative for widespread adoption of Open Science practices. These considerations are particularly relevant to the research field of Indoor Positioning. Open Data and Open Code sharing are gradually gaining traction in the field, but are still far from standard practice. This study comprehensively evaluates the extent of the adoption of Open Science practices within the community of the International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN), by systematically analyzing all reference papers from the 2019 to 2024 editions of the IPIN conference. The work thoroughly examines the Open Data and Code usage, and the use of other types of Open Materials while performing a particular, close-up review of the Open Data that are leveraged in these studies. Our findings reveal that 21.7% of papers use Open Research Data (ORD), 8.3%

utilize Open Code, and 20.2% incorporate other Open Materials. However, only 6.8% of papers provide both Open Data and Code. Moreover, emerging patterns and intuitive best practices are highlighted. The complete characterization of all reviewed publications is publicly available. This study brings to light the need for wider adoption of Open Science practices, to enhance the transparency, reproducibility, replicability, and reliability of research outcomes in the field of Indoor Positioning.

Index Terms— Localization, Positioning, Reproducibility, Open Science, Open Data, Open Code, Open Materials

I. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of Open Science, Research Reproducibility and Transparency has been a central theme in the epistemological debate of the last decade. While the ability to reproduce and replicate experiments and results is a cornerstone of scientific research, it has become a growing realization that in many fields of science, these standards are rarely met.

This is a preprint version. Please consider looking for the eventual published version of the manuscript, which might be available at the time you access the current file. Date of current version 12th of March 2025. (Corresponding author: G.G. Anagnostopoulos). G.G. Anagnostopoulos acknowledges the funding for the research project “CoORDinates”, which initiated this work, by the Swiss Open Research Data Grants (CHORD) in Open Science I, a program coordinated by swissuniversities, and for the research project “CoORDinance” that is provided by the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences. P. Barsocchi and A. Crivello acknowledge funding from European Union - Next Generation EU, in the context of The National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Investment Partenariato Esteso PE8 “Conseguenze e sfide dell’invecchiamento”, Project Age-IT, CUP: B83C22004880006 C. Pendão and I. Silva acknowledge funding by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020 J. Torres-Sospedra acknowledges funding from Generalitat Valenciana (CIDEXG/2023/17, Conselleria d’Educació, Universitats i Ocupació).

G.G. Anagnostopoulos is with the Geneva School of Business Administration, HES-SO, Geneva, Switzerland (e-mail: grigorios.anagnostopoulos@hesge.ch)

P. Barsocchi and A. Crivello are with the Institute of Information Science and Technologies, National Research Council of Italy (e-mail: paolo.barsocchi@isti.cnr.it, antonino.crivello@isti.cnr.it)

C. Pendão is with the Department of Engineering, at the School of Sciences and Technology, University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro, Vila real, Portugal and with Algoritmi Research Centre, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal (e-mail: cristianop@utad.pt)

I. Silva is with Algoritmi Research Centre, University of Minho, 4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal (e-mail: ivo@dsi.uminho.pt)

J. Torres-Sospedra with the Department of Computer Science, Universitat de València, 46100 Burjassot, Spain, and with VALGRAI, Valencian Graduate School and Research Network of Artificial Intelligence, 46022 València, Spain (e-mail: Joaquin.Torres@uv.es)

Fig. 1. Types of Open Resources that the current work analyses within the IPIN community

Researchers often refer to the fact that a great portion of the scientific output fails in replication or reproduction efforts as a ‘Reproducibility crisis’. One of the objectives of Open Science

is to make the content of the whole process of producing evidence and supporting claims transparent and accessible publicly [1], facilitating research reproducibility.

In the field of Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, there has been a slowly increasing tendency to share Open Data and Code [2, 3]. Nevertheless, accompanying research papers with openly sharing the data and code on which the papers were based is still an exception rather than the standard practice in the field. This constitutes a significant decelerating factor in the progress of the field. Due to this barrier, here as in many other research fields as well, works and ideas of high quality remain irreproducible, consistent comparisons of different methods on equal grounds are hardly achieved, and false or erroneous claims remain indefinitely unchallenged [4].

The significance of reproducibility in science and the importance of open science practices have been widely discussed both within and beyond the scientific community. The growing recognition of the importance of transparency, openness, and reproducibility has led policymakers to reassess existing policies and restructure incentive systems [5]. As a result, many funding agencies are adopting measures to support these principles, either by mandating compliance or offering incentives. Policy actions aimed at enhancing reproducibility generally pursue two main objectives: (I) the verifiability and reliability of research outcomes and (II) the fact that the findings contribute value to the broader scientific community beyond their original contributors [5]. Scoping Studies across various disciplines [6–14] often provide a comprehensive and factual overview of the current state of reproducibility within their respective fields. A clear depiction of the relevant status of a certain field can facilitate the decision-making towards positive change. The scoping report of the European Commission describes the fact that *‘there is a growing awareness of the problem in many disciplines, testified by scoping studies and seminal surveys’* [5].

In this context, a recent work advocating for the need for a more Reproducible Indoor Positioning Research by Anagnostopoulos *et al.* [15], suggested that *“an objective understanding of the status of a field can assist the decision-making towards positive change. Therefore, a relevant survey on the current level of reproducibility of indoor positioning research would be an excellent steppingstone and a future baseline to evaluate the progress of the indoor positioning community in this aspect.* Fulfilling this vision, our previous work [16] aimed to contribute to this goal, by providing a comprehensive review of publications from the two most recent editions (2022, 2023) of the International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN), evaluating the extent of the adoption of practices such as the use of open data, open code, and other open material in the publication of the field.

In the current work, we extend the vision and the scope of the conference paper [16]. More specifically, we extend the analysis to papers of three more years, analyzing all reference papers of the IPIN editions between 2019 and 2024 (in 2020 the conference was canceled due to the pandemic). Moreover, we provide a deep dive into the relevant background, a richer analysis of our findings, and a detailed discussion of interest-

ing cases, elaborating on lessons learned and shortcomings. We envisage this contribution as a precious snapshot of the current status of the Open Science practices in the field, which can function as the basis of comparison to measure future improvements.

Focusing on the content of the analysis, for each of the analyzed papers, we analyzed the following aspects (depicted in 1):

- **Characterization of Open Research Data (ORD):** We examined the potential use of (new or preexisting) ORDs within each paper.
- **Characterization of Open Code:** We examined the potential use of open code, defined as openly accessible programming code that can be reused, extended, or adapted by other researchers.
- **Characterization of Open Materials:** Apart from the previous two points (open data and code), we also examined the potential use of new or the reuse of existing open materials. As Open Material, we refer to tools, applications, and resources that facilitate the overall indoor localization workflow or the respective specific task of the paper. Artifacts like executable files, machine learning pre-trained models, and web or mobile applications, were considered Open Materials as they are distinct from the above definition of open code.
- **Detailed Analysis of Papers Using ORD:** All the papers that rely on ORD, went through a fine grained analysis. Several feature families were analyzed, such as the technologies used, the measurement types, the deployment environment types, and characteristics, as well as data utilization aspects.

A high-level overview of the paper is provided by Figure 2. The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section II discusses the relevant background and the related work. The methodology followed in this study is described in detail in Section III, while the subsequent Section IV provides a comprehensive account of the findings of our analysis. Insights, lessons learned, and good practices observed are discussed in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper, offering key takeaways and exploring potential future directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Open Science encompasses practices that make the creation of evidence and the supporting of claims transparent and accessible. Ideals such as transparency and collective scrutiny in scientific research are certainly not a novelty that Open Science aims to introduce, but reflect ideals that are foundational to the scientific Ethos. Robert K. Merton summarized the norms [17] (later referred to as Mertonian norms) defining the Ethos under which the scientific community comprehends and exercises its mission. Two of these norms, ‘Commonality’ and ‘Organized Skepticism’, are central to our current argumentation. ‘Commonality’ emphasizes that scientific goods should be collectively owned to promote collaboration, rejecting secrecy as counterproductive. ‘Organized Skepticism’ advocates for critical scrutiny that scientific claims must face as an integral part of the scientific process. Modern efforts

Fig. 2. An overview of the paper's content

advocating for Open and Reproducible Science aim to realign current practices with these enduring values and to address systemic barriers. Examples of such barriers are the publish or perish logic, the publication bias (systematically favoring novelty over replication), and the undervaluation of rigor in academic incentive structures [18, 19]. Policy interventions, particularly by funding agencies, reflect this shift, seeking to guarantee the validity and wider utility of scientific outcomes, by reimagining the incentives structure throughout the academic landscape [5].

For research communities to be able to enjoy the ‘Commonality’ of scientific goods, and exercise the ‘Organized Skepticism’ by putting all new claims under critical scrutiny, there exist certain prerequisites. From the birth of a research question to formulating a hypothesis, designing an experimental protocol, collecting data, performing analysis, and extracting conclusions, there is a long path of laborious research tasks. A research paradigm where out of all of these laborious steps, only a textual description of a few-page-long research paper gets published, sets itself apart from the direction that the Mertonian norms describe. With no access to the collected data or the precise code implementation of published works, it is often quasi-impossible to precisely reproduce and fairly represent these works in future comparisons. Under a cloud of uncertainty, critical scrutiny can hardly be fairly and efficiently applied.

On the other hand, it is clear that *Reproducibility* and *Replicability* are foundational to scientific progress. At times, different definitions have been assigned to these two terms. On this point, the European Commission’s scoping report on Reproducibility of Scientific Results in the EU [5] aligns with the definitions of *Reproducibility* and *Replicability* as outlined by the American National Academies [20], which nowadays

constitute widely accepted definitions of the terms. Particularly ‘Reproducibility’ entails achieving consistent results using the same data, methods, and conditions, while ‘Replicability’ examines whether consistent outcomes can be achieved in new contexts with different datasets but maintaining the same objectives. Both depend critically on the availability of Open Resources, such as data and code. Nevertheless, mere openness is not sufficient, as the resources must also adhere to certain principles relating to quality and accessibility.

The FAIR principles [21] (standing for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) have emerged as the leading framework for research data sharing. These principles guide researchers in making data universally accessible, accompanied by unique and persistent identifiers, comprehensive metadata, and clear documentation. Metadata should not only describe the structure and attributes of the data but also its provenance and intended use [21]. Moreover, the FAIR principles underscore the importance of registering datasets in searchable repositories and adhering to domain-specific standards to maximize their reusability [21]. While the FAIR principles were originally designed for data management [21], an adaptation of them for research software has been proposed, as the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) principles [22, 23]. While FAIR and FAIR4RS share common goals of improving findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability, FAIR4RS aim to address unique characteristics tailored to software.

Indoor positioning research is inherently data-reliant. The ability to reproduce claims and confirm results hinges on the use of the same data and on the ability to reproduce methods precisely. This often necessitates code sharing to ensure precise reproducibility, as even impressively detailed textual reporting within the published paper might leave sig-

nificant details undisclosed. Furthermore, the ability to fairly represent existing methods is crucial for the evolution of the field. Replicating methods and comparing them consistently with their future counterparts require access to reusable code implementations. Reproducing methods and verifying results or comparing them with other methods in the same settings as the initially used ones, requires access to well-documented and reusable datasets. Performing assisting actions within the overall workflow (data collection and processing, data visualization, etc.) may be facilitated by Open Material, such as data collection mobile applications, domain-specific data visualization frameworks, etc.

It is noteworthy that the vast majority of publications in indoor positioning rely on code implementations and employ data either collected online or recorded in an offline manner. As such, the data and code typically stored in the researchers' workstations are central to the outcomes presented in publications. Consequently, their open sharing significantly strengthens the reliability, reusability, and impact of those publications. Overall, should this become the de facto standard option, it would greatly accelerate the field's progress.

Efforts to promote openness and consistent performance comparisons in indoor positioning have gained traction through initiatives like the recurring IPIN Competition, which provides openly shared datasets and detailed documentation for benchmarking positioning systems. These competitions have been pivotal in fostering comparability in the field [24–33]. However, the field is still far from establishing data sharing as the standard. Many publications rely on undisclosed data or lack detailed descriptions of experimental environments, making reproducibility a challenge [34, 35]. As Adler *et al.* [34] note, without access to shared data and code, reproducing results and assessing methodological advances becomes challenging.

Recent works have tried to shed light on the current availability of ORD within the field. In our recent work on Open Research Data in Indoor Positioning (ORDIP) [36], we systematically reviewed the landscape of the field, identifying 119 open datasets of various technologies, and characterizing numerous relevant features of them. We also discussed best practices and shortcomings and proposed a list of guidelines for the collection and the reuse of such resources. In the same direction, Feng *et al.* [37] focused on the analysis of open WiFi fingerprint datasets, examining the most critical elements of the datasets, identifying challenges, and proposing guidelines for creating new WiFi fingerprint datasets. The current work creates a snapshot of the status of the field regarding the extent of the adoption of Open Science practices and the use of such resources, in a big, representative part of its research production, utilizing the initial data [3] and the methodology, of our previous respective modest effort [2].

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology used in this paper. A total of 397 papers presented at the IPIN conference during the last five editions were reviewed, and their features were systematically evaluated across a range of defined categories.

A. Protocol description

To solidify the reliability of our analysis, we adopted a structured methodological approach, which was described and used in [16]. Each co-author took on dual roles: that of an *'analyst'* and of a *'reviewer.'* Papers were randomly assigned to an analyst-reviewer pair, thus ensuring a balanced distribution among all the possible pairs of team members. The *analyst* was responsible for conducting a detailed examination of each assigned paper, extracting pertinent information, and documenting it systematically in a shared spreadsheet (publicly available in [38]). This process involved reporting specific attributes, such as the presence or absence of Open Research Data (ORD), Open Code, or supplementary materials, as well as providing additional observations or comments for missing or unclear elements.

Following the analyst's work, the assigned *reviewer* critically assessed the entries, suggesting corrections, requesting clarifications, or adding missing information. This often necessitated the reviewer conducting an independent full analysis to validate the analyst's findings. Once the review phase concluded, the *analyst* incorporated the feedback, addressing any discrepancies by accepting proposed changes or engaging in discussions with the *reviewer* to achieve a shared understanding. For particularly ambiguous cases, all co-authors participated in group discussions to resolve issues and reach a consensus. This iterative process not only enhances the accuracy of the characterizations but also ensures a high level of consistency in characterizations across all team members. Regular meetings facilitated alignment in interpreting feature ambiguities and minimized the likelihood of future inconsistencies.

To further enhance uniformity, the produced spreadsheet [38] includes the definitions of the available values for each feature/column, clearly describing their meanings and the logic under which they were characterized. This detailed framework enhances consistency in the characterizations and facilitates systematic cross-verification between analysts and reviewers.

B. Feature characterized

The features extracted from each paper were organized into five distinct categories, each documented in the spreadsheet to facilitate structured characterization:

- **General Information:** This category captured foundational information of the analyzed literature, such as the paper's title, author(s), year of publication, and DOI.
- **Open Research Data (ORD):** In this category, when at least one ORD (pre-existing or new) was used in the analyzed paper, several features related to the use of ORD were characterized. More particularly, we described whether the paper introduced new ORDs or reused existing ones, if the authors exploited one or more datasets, whether the repository is reachable, the dataset publication year, the license of data, and the persistent identifier of the data repository entry (such as a DOI), providing a comprehensive description of data utilization practices. A particular characterization was the data type used, highlighting whether real data were utilized, if authors

relied on simulated data, or even whether a combination of real and simulated data was used. Regarding this data type, we also highlight the cases where no data was used in the papers, often because their adoption was not relevant within the paper (for instance, in theoretical or position papers).

- **Dataset-Specific Features:** This category is only relevant for papers that utilized an ORD dataset, allowing for a deeper analysis of dataset attributes. We assessed the technologies, signal types, and measurements employed, as well as descriptive information regarding the environment (the number of buildings or floors involved, the area’s dimensions, and the potential inclusion of outdoor spaces). File formats, whether subsets for training, validation, and testing were used, and if they were explicitly shared are elements of this analysis.
- **Open Code:** For this category, we evaluated the availability and characteristics of any open code potentially linked to the papers. We first define whether some code related to the paper is made available to the reader, noting whether the paper proposes new code or the authors reuse existing code. Successively, we examine the purpose of the code (e.g., implementing proposed methods, performing the paper’s experiments, or handling dataset loading). Moreover, we describe the programming languages involved in the project, the license under which the code is shared, the potential persistent identifier of the code, and the URL of the code repo, and we also characterize whether the information of the library/software versions used is shared.
- **Open Materials:** This category addressed the presence of supplementary resources like applications, executable files, or mobile apps, specifically related to localization purposes. Such materials were classified and examined for relevance and accessibility. We, therefore, characterize whether some Open Material (e.g., an application, an executable, a mobile app) was used in or proposed in the paper. For this feature, we considered only material related to localization and not general purpose. As previously done for the open code category, we examine whether pre-existing or new open material is used, if the source is cited, and the purpose this material serves (e.g., data collection, data processing, visualization, simulation). Finally, we list the technologies to which the code is related. These can be indoor positioning technologies (e.g., Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, or IMU) or programming technologies.

C. Limitations

All the papers were reviewed over the course of several months, requiring considerable time for in-depth analysis by the team members serving the roles of analysts and reviewers. Understandably, we cannot rule out the possibility that, among the tens of features characterized for hundreds of papers, some feature misclassifications may have infiltrated our analysis, despite the diligent efforts of the team members involved.

Furthermore, while some papers provided useful information relevant to the scope of this article straightforwardly

(e.g., references to DOIs or URLs to external repositories), in many cases, the necessary details were dispersed across multiple sources. For certain papers, it was necessary to explore various assisting websites and directories to identify the desired features. Despite our extensive and rigorous search, we acknowledge that in such cases, there might exist further relevant information that we were unable to access.

This study focuses on papers published at a single conference over the past five years. While we believe that the Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation Conference serves as a key venue for researchers in this field, we recognize that a significant portion of the literature in this domain may remain uncovered. Nevertheless, the strictly defined selection process, the relevance of the venue, and the volume of the analyzed literature provide an informative snapshot of the status of the field.

Lastly, we declare that we aimed to perform the characterizations of the analyzed papers [38] (cumulatively described in Section IV) and the relevant discussion (in Section V) in an objective and factual manner. We strove to follow the Mertonian norms [17] for promoting efforts of ‘*Commonality*’, facilitating the exercise of ‘*Organized Skepticism*’, and relying on predefined, transparently described, objective criteria (serving ‘*Universalism*’). Most importantly, we aimed to incarnate the ‘*Disinterestedness*’ norm and act for the benefit of the community. As witnessed in the paper characterization [38] as well as while highlighting inconsistencies identified in our analysis (Section V), we objectively report inconsistencies and omissions across several works, including numerous relevant works that we have co-authored in the past. The content of the analysis was aimed at a factual description of the status of the field and an indicative exemplification of interesting cases. We welcome potential correction suggestions and remain committed to welcoming constructive feedback.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 3. Data types used in papers from IPIN 2019 until IPIN 2024.

This section describes the findings derived from analyzing all the selected papers. Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of types of data used within the analyzed papers. The majority of the papers (71.79%) rely on real data to produce their results. These data may be obtained from real-world experiments conducted by the authors or from public ORDs. Simulation

Fig. 4. Papers with open resources (open data, code, and material).

data are utilized in 11.59% of the papers, primarily in scenarios where real-world experiments are difficult to conduct due to the limited availability of state-of-the-art hardware. Furthermore, 12.59% of the papers employ a combination of simulated and real data, often using simulation for preliminary tuning and prevalidation of the proposed models, while relying on real data for a realistic evaluation. A small fraction of papers (4.03%) do not utilize any data, typically consisting of survey and position papers or papers that simply present the theoretical framework of an idea.

Figure 4 illustrates the adoption of open resources over the 5-year period considered. The figure provides an analysis of trends in the availability and sharing of open data, code, and materials from 2019 to 2024, as extracted by the analysis of all analyzed papers, available in [38]. The data presented in the table within Figure 4 cover the following categories: openly available data, available code, open materials, papers sharing new ORDs, papers reusing existing code, papers sharing new code, and papers sharing new open materials. The values are reported as percentages. These features form the basis of the plots of Figure 4, which are discussed below.

The upper plot of Figure 4 shows two interesting features. The green line indicates the percentage of papers that use at least one kind of open resource (data OR code OR material) grouped annually for the five analyzed years. In 2019, less than 20% of papers utilized some type of open resources, which increased to around 50% in the following year, followed by a

decline over the next two years, with a slight increase again in 2024. Moreover, the gray line indicates the percentage of papers that use both Open Data AND Open Code. Sharing both data and code may facilitate reproducibility, although by itself, it is not a sufficient condition to achieve it. The trend is positive as years go by, and from 2.44% of papers in 2019, we arrived at 2024 with 8.97% of papers, while the maximum percentage was achieved in 2023 with 10.11%.

The middle plot of Figure 4 shows how the use of open data, open code, or open materials evolved over the five-year period, without making a distinction on whether it was newly shared or reused resources. The usage of openly accessible research data shows a general upward trend over the study period. The percentage of data openly available to the public used in the IPIN papers increased from 11.0% in 2019 to 25.6% in 2024. The shift toward greater open data use has been particularly pronounced during the COVID-19 pandemic when, due to relevant restrictions in accessing public spaces, open data availability rapidly became crucial for facilitating research and collaboration. The overall heightened demand for accessible data likely influenced researchers' attitudes toward open data usage. It also suggests a growing recognition of the importance of data openness in enhancing reproducibility, transparency, and collaboration. The average percentage for the usage of openly available data across the five years stands at 21.7%, reflecting a significant, though not predominant, adoption of open data practices.

Similarly, the usage of open code (new or old), while starting from a lower base, also exhibits a steady increase over time. From 3.7% in 2019, the percentage of available code rose to 11.2% in 2023, though it slightly declined to 9.0% in 2024, with the 5-year average for code availability being at 8.3%. The data indicates a gradual but steady movement towards greater code openness. However, the relatively lower figures compared to data availability highlight that code sharing remains less widespread despite its recognized importance for reproducibility. As indicated in the table of Figure 4, the reuse of existing research code has seen a modest rise between 2019 and 2022, from 1.2% to 4.8%, but the percentage dropped to 0% in 2024. This sharp decline warrants further investigation.

The trend in the availability of open research materials (such as supplementary materials or other open resources beyond data and code) exhibits higher volatility. After a sharp increase to 27.1% in 2021, open material availability peaked at 28.6% in 2022, before declining to 15.7% in 2023 and recovering to 23.1% in 2024. The overall average for open materials stands at 20.2%.

The bottom plot of Figure 4 focuses exclusively on new open resources shared by the analyzed papers. The percentage of papers sharing new ORDs has grown over time, rising from 6.1% in 2019 to 11.5% in 2024, with a five-year average of 7.6%. This increase suggests an encouraging trend toward more researchers making their new data openly available. This rise reflects broader efforts to promote transparency and encourage data reuse in the research community.

The percentage of papers sharing new code has demonstrated a monotonic increase. Starting at 2.4% in 2019, the sharing of new code rose to 9.0% in 2024, with an overall

average of 5.8%. This trend highlights a growing commitment to making new code publicly available, which is critical for enabling reproducibility. However, the overall percentages remain relatively low, suggesting that more efforts are needed to encourage the widespread adoption of open code-sharing practices.

Finally, the sharing of new open materials by authors has remained low throughout the period. From a starting point of 1.2% in 2019, the percentage peaked at 3.2% in 2022 but fell back to 0% in 2024, with an overall average of just 1.5%. The drop to 0% in 2024 may indicate significant barriers or a lack of incentives for researchers to share new materials beyond data and code. Moreover, the striking difference in the average usage of Open Materials (20.2%), and the provision of new ones (1.5%), highlights a potential disparity between their relevance and the incentives for sharing new ones. On the other hand, considering the types of Open Material that are heavily used, such as data collection apps or simulators, it could mean that the existing ones currently cover the needs of the community to a great extent.

Figure 5 presents the results regarding the availability of open data (top), open code (middle), and open material (bottom). This figure complements Fig. 4 by emphasizing specific cases highlighted in our analysis.

The top chart in Figure 5 categorizes instances where open data are either not used, openly accessible, not relevant (e.g., in survey papers), or not reachable. Openly accessible data are available in 21.66% of the papers, while the vast majority (74.81%) do not use open data. Additionally, a small percentage (2.02%) do not include data, such as in survey or analysis papers. Furthermore, we identified six cases (1.51% of the papers) with a claim of using ORD, in which the corresponding datasets were inaccessible due to broken URLs or empty repositories. Similarly, the middle chart in Figure 5 illustrates cases where the cited open code was unavailable (0.76%). In these instances, the repositories were either empty or contained a note indicating that the code would be published soon.

Focusing exclusively on papers that use open research data, whether reused or new, Figure 6 illustrates the presence and usage of different technologies and measurement types. As shown, a diverse range of technologies employed in Indoor Positioning (IP) were identified. The Ultra-Wide Band (UWB) technology stands out with a relatively low adoption rate in the usage of ORD, concerning 5.81% of the analyzed papers, reflecting its still-emerging status. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) shows moderate usage at 9.30%, largely due to its limited applicability in indoor environments. Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) is used in 15.12% of the papers, while cameras are present in 19.77%, indicating their growing prominence in current technological ecosystems. The use of Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) is notably high, with an adoption rate of 37.21%. However, Wi-Fi leads with the highest adoption rate of 46.51%, underscoring its widespread use for positioning purposes. The ‘other technologies’ category collectively accounts for 22.09% of the adoption, regrouping a multitude of technologies like Zigbee, 5G, visual Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) (e.g., using Google Tango),

Fig. 5. Papers using open data (Top); papers using open code (Middle); and, papers using open material (Bottom).

pressure sensors, fiber optic gyroscopes with odometers and altimeters, microphones, and LoRa.

Figure 6 also outlines the types of measurements categorized by technology. In radio technologies such as Wi-Fi or BLE, the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) is predominant due to its simplicity of measurement. Some datasets include more advanced measurements like Time of Flight (TOF) or Channel State Information (CSI), but these are less common as they require specialized hardware and software. Notably, two BLE datasets also include channel information. UWB-based datasets support the collection of CSI, TOF, and Channel Impulse Response (CIR) measurements. For inertial data, most datasets provide accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer data; some only include accelerometer and gyroscope data, while two datasets exclusively offer magnetometer data. GNSS location estimates appear more frequently than raw measurements, likely because they are more readily accessible on devices like smartphones. Lastly, camera-based datasets encompass both images and point clouds (which are often derived from sensors such as Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)).

Regarding the area size of the environment in which the

Fig. 6. Technologies and types of measurements of used ORD.

datasets were collected, Figure 7 illustrates the distribution across different area size classes. For papers utilizing more than one ORD, the dataset corresponding to the largest environment was considered. A significant portion (27.9%) of the analyzed papers involved ORD, for which the area could not be determined due to insufficient metadata. Among the datasets with identifiable area sizes, the majority fall into one of two categories: areas larger than 100,000 m² (25.58%) or between 100 and 1,000 m² (20.93%), primarily associated with Wi-Fi and BLE technologies. Notable examples include UJIIndoorLoc [39], which is widely recognized in the IPIN community for covering multiple multi-floor buildings, and the crowd-sourced dataset [40]. All datasets covering large areas include Wi-Fi data, with some also incorporating BLE, IMU, GNSS, and camera data. In contrast, datasets from smaller environments, with areas ≤ 100 m², typically include Wi-Fi data with RSSI and CSI, BLE data with RSSI and channel information, as well as IMU and Zigbee data.

Figure 8 presents the distribution of open datasets based on the type of environment. Roughly half of the analyzed datasets were collected in office-like environments, including universities, offices, and laboratories. Approximately 24.4% of the papers utilizing ORD explored diverse environmental settings for evaluation and testing, encompassing data from multiple types of environments. These include combinations of residential, office, industrial, and other settings. ‘Other’ specific types of environments account for around 14% of the datasets and represent cases beyond the predefined classes of our analysis, such as simulated or urban scenarios. Shopping centers, residential/home environments, and warehouse/industrial settings collectively represent almost 4% of

Fig. 7. Percentage of papers with open research data based on the area size.

Fig. 8. Percentage of papers with open research data by environment types.

the datasets. Cases where the type of environment could not be identified constitute approximately 8%. We observe that

Fig. 9. Papers using subsets with specific roles (such as train, validation, test sets) that are common in the ML practice (left side) and public availability of such subsets (right side).

there is a high disparity between the level of usage of different environment types. Indeed, office environments represent half of the cases, while environments of high interest for relevant services (industrial, shopping centers, nursing homes) remain severely underrepresented. Understandably, collecting data in the researcher's work environment is the most straightforward way for a researcher, which might explain this unbalanced distribution.

Finally, Figure 9 illustrates the extent to which specific data subsets (such as training, validation, and test sets) are used and shared, typically for predefined roles in the evaluation process commonly, although not exclusively, in ML. The left side of the Sankey plot presents answers to whether such subsets were utilized in papers involving ORD. A typical way of characterizing this is a mention of training and test sets in the papers. The right side of the plot shows whether such subset splits are openly available, and if so, whether the splits were pre-existing or newly created by the authors of the analyzed paper. We can observe that while the majority of works that rely on ORD appear to utilize such a subset distinction (62.79%), it is only in 48.83% of the papers that these subsets are publicly available. Particularly, in 34.88% of the works the sets are predefined before being used by the analyzed works, while in 13.95% of cases, the subsets are newly shared by the authors. Lastly, nearly 14% of works relying on ORD use subsets that are not publicly available, hindering the comparability of their outcomes and the verifiability of their claims, despite their reliance on ORD.

V. DISCUSSION

The analysis of open science practices in the last five editions (at the time of conducting this study) of the IPIN conference provided valuable insights, highlighted shortcomings in open resources, and helped us identify best practices followed by conference participants.

A. High-level insights

The first significant outcome is that 92 out of 397 (23.17%) full regular papers presented in the last five editions of the IPIN conference contain either open data or open code. This value increases to 150 (37.78%) if we also count the papers using open materials related to indoor positioning [35, 41–155]. This can be considered a major milestone in the IPIN conference, as the presence of open materials in the first edition of the conference in 2010 was anecdotal with just 4 contribution, from 133 published regular papers.

While the trend of using open resources is positive, 62.21% of papers still do not report any open resources, hindering the efforts of reproducing them. Thus, we are still far from reaching full transparency on indoor positioning research through fully repeatable, reproducible, and replicable results for the majority of the recent publications. Among the 397 analyzed works, 381 (95.97%) of them rely on data (real measurements, simulation-based data, or a combination of the two). Moreover, due to the nature of the field, it is reasonable that code was implemented or reused to conduct experiments in most works. However, despite the predominance of data and code in the creation of most works, only 27 out of 397

(6.80%) full regular papers presented both open data and code, facilitating reproducibility without ambiguities.

It is noteworthy that researchers presented the data descriptor for an open dataset [156] in the first edition of the IPIN conference in Zurich, Switzerland, back in 2010, evidencing consciousness regarding ORD within the community at that time. Later on, in the tenth edition of the conference held in Pisa, Italy, in 2019, the number of regular papers introducing new ORD was 5 out of 82 (6.09%). The aggregated number of published regular papers in the 2022 and 2023 editions is similar to the number of papers published in 2010, with the main difference being that a total of 11 new ORD have been shared or released within the conference, meaning on average in 2022 and 2023, a 7.24% of published regular papers in these two years presented new ORD. In the 2024 edition in Hong Kong, 9 out of 78 (11.5%) regular papers introduced new ORD. This evidences that the community is becoming more conscious about the relevance of generating and sharing relevant data with the community, doubling the contributions introducing new ORD in the last 5 years.

We have identified a total of 150 regular papers in the last five editions of the IPIN conference providing open resources. Open Research Data (ORD) is present 86 of them, being a core element. Open-source code is only provided in a total of 33 of works, in most of the cases (26 papers) complementing ORD, i.e., in 7 regular papers, code was provided without any new or reused ORD. Finally, 80 regular papers include open materials, such as data collection apps, simulators to generate synthetic data, data processing, or visualization tools, among others. Among these 80 papers, only 22 of them also share ORD or code. i.e., 58 papers use open materials without providing neither ORD nor code.

Anyway, the annual evolution of open research resources is positive. There is a significant increase in the relative use of open data (+146%), open code (+125%), and open materials (+269%) from 2019 to 2021. The pandemic that unraveled from 2020 onward led to the cancellation of the conference that year and brought consequent restrictions on working in public spaces during 2020 and 2021, which may have played a role in this. Due to the restrictions for working at places such as university facilities and performing experiments on-site or collecting new data, it is reasonable for researchers to turn towards the available open resources for continuing their work. The trends in 2022, 2023, and 2024 are, overall, slightly positive with respect to the immediate previous year, meaning that some open research practices have been consolidated.

B. Observed Shortcomings and Best Practices

Before being accepted for publication, all 397 regular papers analyzed in this work passed a stringent peer-review process evaluating their quality. However, their reviewing process was focused on aspects such as: their relationship with the IPIN topics and state of the art, their possible impact on the community, the novelty with respect to the literature, and results. To this day, there is no explicit evaluation criterion for the repeatability, reproducibility, and replicability of the experiments, as these elements are currently implicitly enclosed within the evaluation of the paper's overall soundness.

Similarly, there is no specific evaluation criterion related to the data quality assessment. Nowadays, these evaluation aspects are considered in top conferences and journals. The correct assessment of data and of relevant domain-specific contextual information, such as the evaluation of the environment's suitability, becomes imperative. In this direction, Matey-Sanz *et al.* [58] demonstrated that a wrong use/partition of data might bring unreliable results and conclusions. Another relevant example can be identified in the work by Sinha *et al.* [100], where the authors used a small subset of an open dataset. In that work, data from only one of the 200 buildings covered in the dataset are used. While the dataset is openly available, the reader cannot assess the suitability and generalization of the results for that particular building as the subset used in the study and the potential procedure to select that particular building is unreported.

Regarding Open Code sharing, its usefulness remains relevant even when the data used in their work is not disclosed. For instance, researchers can reuse available code to develop new methods or compare their work to baselines, as does the work by Zhang *et al.* [96]. The authors of [96] proposed the method OW-LOAM based on the open-source *LiDAR Inertial Odometry with Mapping* (LIOM) and compared it to *LiDAR Odometry and Mapping* (LOAM) and two open-source LOAM versions: LOAM-Velodyne and A-LOAM. However, without the open code availability of the new methods, such as the OW-LOAM presented in [96], future researchers cannot replicate or compare against these new solutions, using them as baselines, a fact that limits their impact. Therefore, it is suggested that, beyond the use of the open code of past methods serving as baselines, the open code sharing of the new methods as well, for the accumulation of open and reusable research, and the reliable progress of the field.

The way of citing ORD is the major incoherence that we found in our analysis. A total of 30 regular papers provided ORD and cited the relevant data repository, however, the citation strategies vary. The most commonly met ways of citing the data repositories were the following:

- Hyfte *et al.* [45] cite a data descriptor paper and a data repository in their manuscript.
- Ernst *et al.* [53] provide the link, as a footnote, to the GitHub repository containing ORD and code.
- Kirmaz *et al.* [54] cite the URL of the data repository.
- Pendão *et al.* [57] reference several datasets in the text by providing heterogeneous citations to data repositories, data descriptor papers, and reference papers.
- Skog *et al.* [63] provide at the end of the paper's introduction section a statement about reproducible research, providing in-text the GitLab link.
- Torres-Sospedra *et al.* [35] includes references and citations to all the datasets used in their work, although incoherently, citing data paper descriptors, reference papers in conferences/journals, or data repositories.
- Torres-Sospedra *et al.* [149] cite a Zenodo Package with the synthetic datasets used in the experiments. Despite the fact that the package also contains code for the experiments, there is no mention of the open code implementation in the manuscript.

On the other hand, 55 regular papers used ORD without properly citing the data repository. The ways of referring to the used ORD also vary, with the following being indicative, representative examples:

- Nizharadze *et al.* [47] cite a reference paper when referring to the ORD, and within that paper, a link to the dataset repository is provided.
- Ott *et al.* [55] provide citations to reference papers, which describe either the simulation setup considered in their work or provide the link to a real-world dataset.
- Liang *et al.* [56] cite a related data descriptor paper. The cited work appears to be a preprint currently available exclusively in ResearchGate.
- Guo *et al.* [83] just state in the paper that they used the “TUM RGB-D” dataset, without any reference or citation.
- Luo *et al.* [85] make a reference of *SoLOC* dataset and cite a reference paper, which does not contain any ORD dataset.
- Sinha *et al.* [100] used the UJIIndoorLoc dataset, citing the main URL for the UCI Machine Learning Repository (which contains numerous datasets) and not the dataset’s URL.
- Raza *et al.* [104] uses two ORD, providing a reference to a `github.io` website and a reference paper in the IROS conference. However, for the `github.io`, we were able to reach the data after following a non-trivial sequence of links. Data were on a separate `github.io` repository.
- Torres-Sospedra *et al.* [35] cited previous works using the same ORD but cited neither the original data repositories nor the reference/data-descriptor papers.
- Silva *et al.* [124] used a dataset which, at the moment their paper was published, was not openly available but was later released in Zenodo.
- Flueratoru *et al.* [132] declared the usage of a public dataset, which was described partially in their previous paper cited in [132], and within which the URL of the data repository appears as a footnote.
- Shoushtari *et al.* [157] cited three reference papers for the three ORDs used, in one of which the links provided to data are broken.

The FAIR principles [21], outlined in Section II, recommend citing the source of data (i.e., the data repository) to ensure proper attribution and traceability. Specifically, F2 (Findability) highlights that clear citation, including repository information, helps others locate the data, while A1 (Accessibility) emphasizes that repository citations ensure that data remains accessible via persistent identifiers. When a dataset is also supported by a data descriptor (e.g., a publication detailing its creation and context), it is recommended to cite both the repository and the descriptor. This practice aligns with R1.1 (Reusability), as descriptors provide additional metadata for effective reuse, and I1 (Interoperability), as citing both maintains links between data and its context. While citing the data descriptor alone ensures credit to authors, also including the repository citation strengthens compliance with FAIR principles by enhancing findability and reusability. Most major repositories –like Zenodo, IEEE DataPort, or the University

of California - Irvine (UCI) repository of machine learning– provide standardized tools for exporting citations to several formats and bibliography managers, facilitating the proper citations.

Our analysis has shown that there is no standard part of a paper where the citation to the ORD is made. We have found citations to the ORD in the introduction [47, 63], proposed method [45, 54], evaluation pipeline [57], in the analysis/results [64], and, even, in a dedicated reproducibility section before references [59]. Furthermore, citations to the ORD can also be found as a title footnote [114] or within the paper’s abstract [16]. We consider it imperative to uniformize the way ORD are referenced in publications. Regarding this, we strongly recommend providing an unnumbered section “Data Usage and Reproducibility” before the references list (as we do in this manuscript) where it should be clear which open and private/restricted datasets and code, have been used within the manuscript. Moreover, if other open materials (such as a simulator or a data collection app) were used, and were crucial to the execution of the work, they are to be reported as well. Furthermore, the description of the open resources should include the corresponding full proper citations in the references list.

When referring to datasets or other open materials within a research paper, authors usually use a short version of the full name. Such short names or acronyms are often proposed by the dataset creators within the data descriptor or the data repository. However, some datasets are published with long titles without providing such short names. In those cases, the authors using them often come up with a short name for ease of reference to the dataset in their paper. This might create different names of reference for the same data source, even when authors aim to select a representative short name. An example of an ambiguity caused by this and be found in the work by Baskin *et al.* [44] in which the authors named a dataset *Miskolc* (original sources in [158, 159]) but, according to the context and GitHub repository [160], they were using and citing a different long-term dataset collected in a library [161, 162]. It is advised to the dataset donors to provide every dataset with a short name or acronym, to avoid any ambiguity and facilitate reference to their dataset.

Despite being less than 5 years old, we found that the resources of a few works are not available. Often, this happens because the used open dataset was not hosted in a repository ensuring long-term preservation, such as the *Alcala Tutorial* dataset used in Baskin *et al.* [44]. It may also happen that the authors cite a data descriptor that does not contain any hyperlink to data, making it impossible to reach the dataset. For instance, Luo *et al.* [85] cited the paper [163] as the reference for the SoLoc dataset, a fact that did not allow us to find that dataset. Finally, there are papers that claim to share new ORDs, which are unavailable. For instance, Cheng *et al.* [164] mentions that ‘*Full code and data can be accessed at*’ a provided GitHub link, but the repository contains no data at the time of writing this manuscript, displaying this message in the descriptor “*We are currently preparing the code and dataset for public release. It will be made available soon. Stay tuned!*”. Another example is in Skog *et al.* [165], where the

SUMMARY OF THE BEST PRACTICES TO BE FOLLOWED

✓ BEST PRACTICES	👉 RECOMMENDATION
Sharing Open Code	It is recommended to share the code for new proposed methods, allowing the community to enhance the replicability of such methods in unseen scenarios.
Sharing New Open Research Data	When unpublished data are used in experiments, it is recommended to share them openly, allowing the community not only to reproduce the work but also to expand the set of benchmark datasets for testing existing methods .
Information about ORD Subsets	When using parts of a public dataset or when defining specific subsets , such as training, validation, and test sets, all relevant information about these subsets should be shared to ensure the work can be reproduced.
Formal Citation	It is recommended to formally cite the repository hosting the dataset and the data descriptor paper (if available), within an unnumbered section “Data Usage and Reproducibility” before the references list, therefore avoiding giving url's as footnotes or ambiguous references. Major repositories provide the indications for a formal citation in different formats.
Long-Term Repository	Open Data and Code should be provided in long-term preserving repositories providing persistent unique identifiers, such as DOI. The use of personal websites, and personal account pages on data-and-code-sharing platforms, while practical, is discouraged if they do not ensure long-term preservation.
Availability of Data at Review Stage	In cases where promising data or code will be made available only after the review stage, once the paper is accepted, authors and editors must ensure that the data are accessible at the camera-ready submission stage to prevent broken references to non-existent datasets.
Information about Secondary Data	The use of secondary data requires proper citation of the original dataset as well as the publication of the derived data according to the main dataset's license. Moreover, the script/model producing the secondary data should also be shared .

Fig. 10. Summary of the best practices to be followed

authors state that “*All the data and code used to produce the presented results can be downloaded from www.openshoe.se.*”, which is unreachable.

The reason for encountering unreachable empty repositories may vary. Empty repositories may be due to the fact that the dataset's release is postponed after the paper's acceptance, and this last step might be omitted, incidentally or not. An unreachable website (where the link is not working) may appear because the page was never released, because the relevant project website has been discontinued, or the responsible author left the institution. In any case, it would be advisable that a check is made in the camera-ready version of the manuscripts, and any claim of data availability that cannot be met at that time should be removed. Moreover, the timely deposit of data to repositories guaranteeing long-time preservation of the data would help avoid such problems of inaccessibility. The examples of the previous paragraph are provided to demonstrate that arguing for accessibility guarantees is not a theoretical argument, but it would address issues identified in practice, as demonstrated by those described cases identified within the last five editions of the IPIN conference.

Beyond our initial methodological choice to make the distinction of the data used between *Simulated* and *Real data*, we have identified another interesting characteristic data type: measured data that has been further processed to generate new data. Apart from the traditional secondary datasets, which involve format changes, data aggregation, or removal of unnecessary data, there are datasets whose data were generated by models fed with real measurements to generate artificial measurements in new locations within the operational area.

These models are not limited to the traditional interpolation or extrapolation models –such as Gaussian Process Regression used for some datasets in [64]– but also include tailored interpolation algorithms inspired by genetic algorithms [114], translation/rotation (see [41]) or advanced generative models based on deep learning (see [73, 166]). When publishing a secondary dataset derived from a primary public dataset (permitted by its license), authors are expected to provide the scripts used for its creation. Moreover, it is advisable that the original dataset is credited, even if attribution isn't required, for transparency, verifiability, and reproducibility.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted a thorough analysis of paper contributions presented at the IPIN conference in the last five editions, emphasizing the adoption and dissemination of open data, open-source code, and supplementary open materials. These resources are crucial for fostering transparency and reproducibility in evaluation practices. Our systematic analysis focused on those works with usage or contribution of ORD, open-source code, and other publicly available materials, and provided an in-depth analysis of the ORDs used, characterizing technologies employed, types of measurements, environments studied, and utilization techniques. The main objectives of this work were to provide a factual description of the status of the adoption of these open science practices in the field of indoor positioning research, and to promote a culture of transparency and openness in it, identifying areas for improvement and supporting the shift toward more robust and reproducible scientific practices.

Undoubtedly, the results indicate that the International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN) conference has evolved in the last years. It had marginal contributions engaging with Open Science practices in the first edition in 2010 with 4 relevant reference papers, and a single data descriptor paper, out of a total of 133 papers. Since then, significant initiatives, such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) and the publication of the FAIR principles [21] (in 2012 and 2016 respectively), have impacted the perception of the research community about the importance of Open Science and the foundational significance of many of its practices. Nine years later, in 2019, the percentage of works utilizing any type of open resources was slightly below 20%, representing an increase of approximately $\times 6$ with respect to the first edition. Since 2020, there has been another significant increase in open science practices within the positioning community. In the last edition (2024), the percentage of works with any open resources was approximately 45%, representing an increase of approximately $\times 15$ with respect to the first edition and $\times 2.5$ with respect to 2019.

Over the last five editions, 21.7% of the published reference works include ORDs. Among these, nearly 40% of them contribute with new datasets that can be reused in further research, while the remaining 60% utilize existing datasets enabling direct comparisons with previous literature. The research community is actively incorporating ORDs not only to allow fair comparisons with state-of-the-art methods but also to contribute with new datasets, thereby enriching the options for a benchmark repository for indoor positioning, localization, navigation, and tracking. Nevertheless, there is still plenty of room for improvement. Indicatively, in IPIN 2024, the new datasets are shared primarily through personal GitHub repositories, a practice that does not guarantee the longevity of the data availability, as requested by the FAIR principles. Guaranteeing long-term preservation of ORDs can facilitate and promote the use of public datasets.

With the exception of recent modest efforts [36, 37] contributing in this direction, we observe a lack of clear guidelines for publishing open resources within the indoor positioning research field. This fact evidences the need to define a code of conduct for the sharing of Open Data and Code for the IPIN research community, which is our immediate future work. This code should clearly define new evaluation criteria to assess the contributions in terms of reproducibility with special emphasis on open digital assets. More specifically, the code should provide guidance on how to contribute ORDs according to the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) guidelines and the domain specificities, as well as how to review and evaluate works claiming open materials.

As a first step, we have provided recommendations to the IPIN's Technical Program Committee to introduce open science practices within the evaluations of the conference submissions, and we are elaborating the guidelines to assess them in the review process. As a result, the conference is now emphasizing open science practices in the call for papers, indicating that papers with an open science component will be positively received during the review process. The goal is to solidify this practice so that, through time, it becomes the de

facto standard option of publications in the field. We invite the community to embrace this approach, which will help to collectively provide a tremendous push to the research of our field.

DATA USAGE AND REPRODUCIBILITY

All data of our analysis are openly available in [38].

CREDIT AUTHOR STATEMENT

Grigorios G. Anagnostopoulos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Paolo Barsocchi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Antonino Crivello:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cristiano Pendão:** Writing review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ivo Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joaquín Torres-Sospedra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

All authors have contributed equally for almost a year to this work and can all be considered the main authors of this manuscript.

APPENDIX I

LIST OF ANALYZED PAPERS WITH OPEN MATERIALS

Tables I and II introduce the 397 papers that we have identified and analyzed in this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. R. Munafò *et al.*, “A manifesto for reproducible science,” en, *Nature Human Behaviour*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–9, Jan. 2017, Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-016-0021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-016-0021>.
- [2] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, P. Barsocchi, A. Crivello, C. Pendão, I. Silva, and J. Torres-Sospedra, *Evaluating open science practices in indoor positioning and indoor navigation research*, en, 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13684170. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/13684170>.
- [3] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, P. Barsocchi, A. Crivello, C. Pendão, I. Silva, and J. Torres-Sospedra, *Evaluating open science practices in indoor positioning and indoor navigation research (supplementary material: Full paper listing and analysis)*, en, 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12088175. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/12088175>.
- [4] B. A. Nosek, J. R. Spies, and M. Motyl, “Scientific Utopia: II. Restructuring Incentives and Practices to Promote Truth Over Publishability,” en, *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 615–631, Nov. 2012. DOI: 10.1177/1745691612459058. [Online]. Available: <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1745691612459058> (visited on 03/27/2024).
- [5] European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., *Reproducibility of scientific results in the EU: scoping report*. eng. LU: Publications Office, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/341654>.

- [6] S. Laraway, S. Snycerski, S. Pradhan, and B. E. Huitema, "An Overview of Scientific Reproducibility: Consideration of Relevant Issues for Behavior Science/Analysis," *Perspectives on Behavior Science*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 33–57, Mar. 2019. DOI: 10.1007/s40614-019-00193-3. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40614-019-00193-3> (visited on 01/24/2025).
- [7] V. Edefonti *et al.*, "Reproducibility of A Posteriori Dietary Patterns across Time and Studies: A Scoping Review," eng, *Advances in Nutrition (Bethesda, Md.)*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 1255–1281, Sep. 2020. DOI: 10.1093/advances/nmaa032.
- [8] D. J. Niven *et al.*, "Reproducibility of clinical research in critical care: A scoping review," *BMC Medicine*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 26, Feb. 2018. DOI: 10.1186/s12916-018-1018-6. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-018-1018-6> (visited on 01/24/2025).
- [9] K. D. Cobey *et al.*, "Epidemiological characteristics and prevalence rates of research reproducibility across disciplines: A scoping review of articles published in 2018–2019," *eLife*, vol. 12, D. B. Allison, M. Zaidi, C. J. Vorland, A. Lupia, and J. Agle, Eds., e78518, Jun. 2023, Publisher: eLife Sciences Publications, Ltd. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.78518. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.78518> (visited on 01/24/2025).
- [10] J. H. Stage, D. E. Rosenberg, A. M. Abdallah, H. Akbar, N. A. Attallah, and R. James, "Assessing data availability and research reproducibility in hydrology and water resources," *Scientific Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 190030, Feb. 2019. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2019.30. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2019.30>.
- [11] N. Bonneel, D. Coeurjolly, J. Digne, and N. Mellado, "Code replicability in computer graphics," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 39, no. 4, Jul. 2020. DOI: 10.1145/3386569.3392413. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3386569.3392413>.
- [12] O. B. Amaral, K. Neves, A. P. Wasilewska-Sampaio, and C. F. Carneiro, "The Brazilian Reproducibility Initiative," eng, *eLife*, vol. 8, e41602, Feb. 2019. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.41602.
- [13] P. Kedron, W. Li, S. Fotheringham, and M. Goodchild, "Reproducibility and replicability: Opportunities and challenges for geospatial research," *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 427–445, Mar. 2021, Publisher: Taylor & Francis. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2020.1802032>. DOI: 10.1080/13658816.2020.1802032. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2020.1802032> (visited on 01/24/2025).
- [14] M. Collombin *et al.*, "Geospatial Webservices and Reproducibility of Research: Challenges and Needs," en, in *Web and Wireless Geographical Information Systems*, M. Lotfian and L. L. L. Starace, Eds., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 86–92. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-60796-7_6.
- [15] G. G. Anagnostopoulos and A. Kalousis, "Towards Reproducible Indoor Positioning Research," in *Work-in-Progress Papers 11th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN 2021)*, ser. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, vol. 3097, 2021.
- [16] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, P. Barsocchi, A. Crivello, C. Pendão, I. Silva, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "Evaluating Open Science Practices in Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation Research: A Survey of the IPIN's Reference Papers of 2022 and 2023 Editions," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786134. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786134/>.
- [17] R. K. Merton, *The sociology of science: theoretical and empirical investigations*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1973.
- [18] A. Cockburn, P. Dragicevic, L. Besançon, and C. Gutwin, "Threats of a replication crisis in empirical computer science," en, *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 63, no. 8, pp. 70–79, Jul. 2020. DOI: 10.1145/3360311. [Online]. Available: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3360311>.
- [19] D. Moher *et al.*, "The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity," en, *PLOS Biology*, vol. 18, no. 7, e3000737, Jul. 2020. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>.
- [20] Committee on Reproducibility and Replicability in Science *et al.*, *Reproducibility and Replicability in Science*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press, Sep. 2019, Pages: 25303. DOI: 10.17226/25303. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nap.edu/catalog/25303>.
- [21] M. D. Wilkinson *et al.*, "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship," en, *Scientific Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 160018, Mar. 2016, Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>.
- [22] D. S. Katz, M. Gruenpeter, and T. Honeyman, "Taking a fresh look at fair for research software," *Patterns*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 100222, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100222>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666389921000362>.
- [23] M. Barker *et al.*, "Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software," en, *Scientific Data*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 622, Oct. 2022, Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group. DOI: 10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01710-x>.
- [24] F. Potortù, P. Barsocchi, M. Girolami, J. Torres-Sospedra, and R. Montoliu, "Evaluating indoor localization solutions in large environments through competitive benchmarking: The EvAAL-ETRI competition," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, Oct. 2015, pp. 1–10. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2015.7346970. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7346970>.
- [25] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "The Smartphone-Based Offline Indoor Location Competition at IPIN 2016: Analysis and Future Work," en, *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 3, p. 557, Mar. 2017, Number: 3 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. DOI: 10.3390/s17030557. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/3/557>.
- [26] F. Potortù *et al.*, "Comparing the Performance of Indoor Localization Systems through the EvAAL Framework," en, *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 10, p. 2327, Oct. 2017, Number: 10 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. DOI: 10.3390/s17102327. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/10/2327>.
- [27] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "A realistic evaluation of indoor positioning systems based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting: The 2015 EvAAL-ETRI competition," en, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart Environments*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 263–279, Jan. 2017, Publisher: IOS Press. DOI: 10.3233/AIS-170421. [Online]. Available: <https://content.iospress.com/articles/journal-of-ambient-intelligence-and-smart-environments/ais421>.
- [28] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "Off-Line Evaluation of Mobile-Centric Indoor Positioning Systems: The Experiences from the 2017 IPIN Competition," en, *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 2, p. 487, Feb. 2018, Number: 2 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. DOI: 10.3390/s18020487. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/18/2/487>.
- [29] M. C. Pérez-Rubio *et al.*, "A realistic evaluation of indoor robot position tracking systems: The IPIN 2016 competition experience," *Measurement*, vol. 135, pp. 151–162, Mar. 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.measurement.2018.11.018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224118310728>.
- [30] F. Potortù, A. Crivello, and F. Palumbo, "11 - The EvAAL Evaluation Framework and the IPIN Competitions," in *Geographical and Fingerprinting Data to Create Systems for Indoor Positioning and Indoor/Outdoor Navigation*, ser. Intelligent Data-Centric Systems, J. Conesa, A. Pérez-Navarro, J. Torres-Sospedra, and R. Montoliu, Eds., Academic Press, Jan. 2019, pp. 209–224. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-12-813189-3.00011-3. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128131893000113>.
- [31] F. Potortù *et al.*, "The IPIN 2019 Indoor Localisation Competition—Description and Results," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 206674–206718, 2020, Conference Name: IEEE Access. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3037221. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9253514>.
- [32] F. Potortù *et al.*, "Off-Line Evaluation of Indoor Positioning Systems in Different Scenarios: The Experiences from IPIN 2020 Competition," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 5011–5054, Mar. 2022, Conference Name: IEEE Sensors Journal. DOI: 10.1109/JSEN.2021.3083149. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9439493>.
- [33] F. Potortù *et al.*, "Offsite evaluation of localization systems: Criteria, systems and results from IPIN 2021–22 competitions," *IEEE Journal of Indoor and Seamless Positioning and Navigation*, pp. 1–39, 2024,

- Conference Name: IEEE Journal of Indoor and Seamless Positioning and Navigation. DOI: 10.1109/JISPIN.2024.3355840. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10404047>.
- [34] S. Adler, S. Schmitt, K. Wolter, and M. Kyas, "A survey of experimental evaluation in indoor localization research," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, Banff, AB, Canada: IEEE, Oct. 2015, pp. 1–10. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2015.7346749. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7346749/>.
- [35] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "Towards Ubiquitous Indoor Positioning: Comparing Systems across Heterogeneous Datasets," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662560.
- [36] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, P. Barsocchi, A. Crivello, C. Pendão, I. Silva, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "ORDIP: Principle, practice and guidelines for open research data in indoor positioning," *Internet of Things*, p. 101485, Jan. 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.iot.2024.101485. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2542660524004268> (visited on 01/09/2025).
- [37] X. Feng, K. An Nguyen, and Z. Luo, "A review of open access wifi fingerprinting datasets for indoor positioning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 167970–167989, 2024. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3496561.
- [38] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, A. C. Paolo Barsocchi, C. Pendão, I. Silva, and J. Torres-Sospedra, *Comprehensive assessment of open science practices in indoor positioning: Open data, code and material (supplementary material: Full paper listing and analysis)*, en, 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14523896. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/14523896>.
- [39] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "Ujiindoorloc: A new multi-building and multi-floor database for wlan fingerprint-based indoor localization problems," in *2014 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, 2014, pp. 261–270. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2014.7275492.
- [40] E. S. Lohan, J. Torres-Sospedra, P. Richter, H. Leppäkoski, J. Huerta, and A. Cramariuc, *Crowdsourced WiFi database and benchmark software for indoor positioning*, Oct. 2017. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1001662. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/1001662>.
- [41] F. Parralejo, J. A. Paredes, F. J. Aranda, F. J. Alvarez, and J. A. Moreno, "Millimetre Wave Radar System for Safe Flight of Drones in Human-Transited Environments," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332501.
- [42] Y. Dong, T. Arslan, and Y. Yang, "A Multimodal Graph Fingerprinting Method for Indoor Positioning Systems," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332496.
- [43] Y. Busnel and H. Rivano, "FTM-Broadcast: Efficient Network-wide Ranging," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332504.
- [44] A. Baskin, B. T. Nixon, P. K. Chrysanthis, C. Laoudias, and C. Costa, "RETSINA: Reproducibility and Experimentation Testbed for Signal-Strength Indoor Near Analysis," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332500.
- [45] Z. V. Hyfte and A. Zakhor, "Close-Range Indoor Proximity Detection for COVID-19 Exposure Notifications Using Smartphone Magnetometer Traces," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332498.
- [46] S. Kastner, M. Ebner, M. Bullmann, T. Fetzer, F. Deinzer, and M. Grzegorzek, "SIMUL: Synchronized IMU Dataset of Walking People at Six Body Locations," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332491.
- [47] N. Nizharadze, M. Mahlig, and T. Merk, "Simulation of machine learning inferences in real-time operating system to improve direction finding in an embedded environment," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332487.
- [48] A. Foliadis, M. H. C. García, R. A. Stirling-Gallacher, X. Gong, and R. S. Thomä, "Deep Learning based Positioning with Beamformed CSI Fingerprints," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332494.
- [49] B. Siebler, T. Gerstewitz, S. Sand, and U. D. Hanebeck, "Magnetic Field-based Indoor Localization of a Tracked Robot with Simultaneous Calibration," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332492.
- [50] F. Elyasi and R. Manduchi, "Step Length Is a More Reliable Measurement Than Walking Speed for Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332483.
- [51] K. Shao, Z. Li, M. Shu, Q. Guo, and Q. Wu, "Smartphone-Based Multi-Mode Geomagnetic Matching/PDR Integrated Indoor Positioning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332481.
- [52] N. Agarwal, K. O'Keefe, and R. Klukas, "Alternative Approach to Integrate GNSS Doppler in Kalman Filter for Smartphone Positioning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332485.
- [53] D. Ernst, S. Vogel, I. Neumann, and H. Alkhatib, "Error State Kalman Filter with Implicit Measurement Equations for Position Tracking of a Multi-Sensor System with IMU and LiDAR," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332480.
- [54] A. Kirmaz, T. Sahin, D. S. Michalopoulos, and W. H. Gerstaecker, "Time-based vs. Fingerprinting-based Positioning Using Artificial Neural Networks," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332472.
- [55] J. Ott, M. Stahlke, S. Kram, T. Feigl, and C. Mutschler, "Multipath Delay Estimation in Complex Environments using Transformer," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332470.
- [56] Q. Liang, G. Zhang, and L.-T. Hsu, "An empirical multi-wall NLOS ranging model for Wi-Fi RTT indoor positioning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332471.
- [57] C. G. Pendão, I. Silva, A. J. C. Moreira, F. J. Aranda, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "Towards Quality Wi-Fi Synthetic Data for Indoor Positioning Evaluation," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332218.
- [58] M. Matey-Sanz, J. Torres-Sospedra, and A. J. C. Moreira, "Temporal Stability on Human Activity Recognition based on Wi-Fi CSI," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332214.
- [59] F. J. Aranda, F. Parralejo, T. Aguilera, F. J. Alvarez, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "RSS Channel-Based Integration for BLE Fingerprinting Positioning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332223.

- [60] N. Joswig, A. Morrison, N. Sokolova, and L. Ruotsalainen, "Towards Robust Visual Inertial Odometry in Feature Sparse Structured Environments," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332216.
- [61] F. Rasp, E. Eberlein, B. Perner, E. Roth-Mandutz, and S. Hipp, "Enhanced 5G Sidelink Ranging Based on Carrier Aggregation," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332548.
- [62] I. Silva, C. G. Pendão, J. Torres-Sospedra, and A. J. C. Moreira, "Overcoming Radio Map Degradation in Wi-Fi-based Positioning Systems," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332545.
- [63] I. Skog, G. Hendeby, and M. Kok, "Tightly Integrated Motion Classification and State Estimation in Foot-Mounted Navigation Systems," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332538.
- [64] J. Torres-Sospedra et al., "Let's Talk about k-NN for Indoor Positioning: Myths and Facts in RF-based Fingerprinting," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332535.
- [65] M. Sugimoto, M. Suenaga, H. Watanabe, M. Nakamura, and H. Hashizume, "Smartphone Indoor Positioning using Inertial and Ambient Light Sensors," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332528.
- [66] N. Moayeri, "Cooperative Localization Using Received Signal Strength and Least Squares Estimation Methods," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332522.
- [67] S. L. Plaza, J. Torres-Sospedra, J. J. G. Domínguez, J. M. V. Carrizo, and A. J. Martín, "Unsupervised Analysis of Daily Routine Evolution for Elderly People Using Room-Level Localisation," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332525.
- [68] X. Feng, K. A. Nguyen, and Z. Luo, "A dynamic model switching algorithm for WiFi fingerprinting indoor positioning," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332521.
- [69] X. Ma and S. Särkkä, "Indoor Positioning Methods Based on Dual Feet-Mounted IMUs With Distance Constraints," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332511.
- [70] T. Bravenc, J. Torres-Sospedra, M. Gould, and T. Fryza, "UJI Probes: Dataset of Wi-Fi Probe Requests," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332508.
- [71] M. Kabiri, C. Cimorelli, H. Bavle, J. L. Sánchez-López, and H. Voos, "Pose Graph Optimization for a MAV Indoor Localization Fusing 5GNR TOA with an IMU," in *13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2023, Nuremberg, Germany, September 25-28, 2023*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN57070.2023.10332506.
- [72] M. Laska, T. Schulz, J. Grottko, C. Blut, and J. Blankenbach, "VI-SLAM2tag: Low-Effort Labeled Dataset Collection for Fingerprinting-Based Indoor Localization," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918148.
- [73] D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, and J. Huerta, "SURIMI: Supervised Radio Map Augmentation with Deep Learning and a Generative Adversarial Network for Fingerprint-based Indoor Positioning," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918146.
- [74] C. D. Cock, S. Coene, B. V. Herbruggen, L. Martens, W. Joseph, and D. Plets, "IMU-aided detection and mitigation of Human Body Shadowing for UWB positioning," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918139.
- [75] F. S. Danis, "Live RSSI Filtering for Indoor Positioning with Bluetooth Low-Energy," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918138.
- [76] H. Fu, Y. Kone, V. Renaudin, and N. Zhu, "A Survey on Artificial Intelligence for Pedestrian Navigation with Wearable Inertial Sensors," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918136.
- [77] T. Bravenc, J. Torres-Sospedra, M. Gould, and T. Fryza, "What Your Wearable Devices Revealed About You and Possibilities of Non-Cooperative 802.11 Presence Detection During Your Last IPIN Visit," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918134.
- [78] J. Lu et al., "ONavi: Data-driven based Multi-sensor Fusion Positioning System in Indoor Environments," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918137.
- [79] K. Kostas, R. Y. Kostas, F. Zampella, and F. Alshely, "WiFi Based Distance Estimation Using Supervised Machine Learning," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918128.
- [80] H. Zhao, X. Ji, D. Wei, and J. Zhang, "Online IMU-Odometer Extrinsic Calibration Based on Visual-Inertial-Odometer Fusion for Ground Vehicles," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918125.
- [81] V. Upadhyay, K. Roy, and M. Balakrishnan, "Beacon Placement and Signal Strength Estimation to Improve Localization Coverage and Accuracy," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918130.
- [82] B. Zi, H. Wang, J. Santos, and H. Zheng, "An Enhanced Visual SLAM Supported by the Integration of Plane Features for the Indoor Environment," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918123.
- [83] Z. Guo, X. Ji, D. Wei, C. Xie, and J. Zhang, "The Semantic Point & Line SLAM for Indoor Dynamic Environment," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918122.
- [84] S. Tiku, D. Gufran, and S. Pasricha, "Multi-Head Attention Neural Network for Smartphone Invariant Indoor Localization," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918120.
- [85] X. Luo and N. Meratnia, "A Geometric Deep Learning Framework for Accurate Indoor Localization," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918118.
- [86] Y. Dong, T. Arslan, Y. Yang, and Y. Ma, "A WiFi Fingerprint Augmentation Method for 3-D Crowdsourced Indoor Positioning Systems," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918117.

- [87] Y. Dong, T. Arslan, and Y. Yang, "An Encoded LSTM Network Model for WiFi-based Indoor Positioning," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918116.
- [88] L. Wang and S. Pasricha, "A Framework for CSI-Based Indoor Localization with ID Convolutional Neural Networks," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918112.
- [89] M. Bullmann, T. Fetzer, M. Ebner, S. Kastner, F. Deinzer, and M. Grzegorzec, "Data Driven Sensor Model for Wi-Fi Fine Timing Measurement," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918111.
- [90] H. Chen and A. Dhekne, "PnPLoc: UWB Based Plug & Play Indoor Localization," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918119.
- [91] H. Zeaiter, F. Spies, O. Baala, and T. Val, "Measuring accurate Angle of Arrival of weak LoRa signals for Indoor Positioning," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918114.
- [92] X. Xu, A. Peng, and X. Hong, "Unscented Kalman Filtering Based Multipath-assisted Positioning with Peak Flow Tracking," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918113.
- [93] M. Sun, Y. Wang, K. Liu, C. D. Cock, W. Joseph, and D. Plets, "Smartphone-based WiFi FTM Fingerprinting Approach with Map-aided Particle Filter," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918110.
- [94] A.-V. Vu and D. Han, "An IoT Based Approach for Platform Independent Positioning Service," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918103.
- [95] M. Ebner, T. Fetzer, M. Bullmann, S. Kastner, F. Deinzer, and M. Grzegorzec, "PIPF: Proposal-Interpolating Particle Filter," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918102.
- [96] Z. Zhang, Z. Yao, and M. Lu, "OW-LOAM: Observation-Weighted LiDAR Odometry and Mapping," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918105.
- [97] H. Chen and A. Dhekne, "A Metric for Quantifying UWB Ranging Error Due to Clock Drifts," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9918104.
- [98] J. Schyga, S. Plambeck, J. Hinckeldeyn, G. Fey, and J. Kreutzfeldt, "Decision Trees for Analyzing Influences on the Accuracy of Indoor Localization Systems," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9917515.
- [99] J. Coulin, R. Guillemard, V. Gay-Bellile, C. Joly, and A. d. L. Fortelle, "Online Magnetometer Calibration in Indoor Environments for Magnetic field-based SLAM," in *12th IEEE International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2022, Beijing, China, September 5-8, 2022*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN54987.2022.9917514.
- [100] S. Sinha and D. V. Le, "Completely Automated CNN Architecture Design Based on VGG Blocks for Fingerprinting Localisation," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662642.
- [101] S. Sosnin, A. Lomayev, and A. Khoryaev, "DL-AOD Positioning Algorithm for Enhanced 5G NR Location Services," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662638.
- [102] V. Tormo, F. Seco, and A. R. Jiménez, "Design of an RFID-based positioning system for safety of personnel in nuclear facilities," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662629.
- [103] H. Shoushtari, C. Askar, D. Harder, T. Willemsen, and H. Sternberg, "3D Indoor Localization using 5G-based Particle Filtering and CAD Plans," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662636.
- [104] A. Raza, L. Lolic, S. Akhter, and M. Liut, "Comparing and Evaluating Indoor Positioning Techniques," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662632.
- [105] P. Isaia, C. Laoudias, A. Kamilaris, and C. G. Panayiotou, "CovTracer-EN: The Journey of Covid-19 Digital Contact Tracing in Cyprus," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662621.
- [106] P. Josephy, S. Tanner, and R. Wattenhofer, "Combined ADS-B and GNSS Indoor Localization," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662620.
- [107] C. Zhang, D. Yankov, S. Shapiro, and W. Wu, "An End-to-end Beacon Placement Optimization System for Indoor Positioning," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662619.
- [108] H. Ai, T. Hu, and T. Xu, "RAD-GAN: Radio Map Anomaly Detection for Fingerprint Indoor Positioning with GAN," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662616.
- [109] T. Feigl, E. Eberlein, S. Kram, and C. Mutschler, "Robust ToA-Estimation using Convolutional Neural Networks on Randomized Channel Models," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662625.
- [110] C. Huang, H. Lin, H. Lin, H. Liu, Z. Gao, and L. Huang, "YO-VIO: Robust Multi-Sensor Semantic Fusion Localization in Dynamic Indoor Environments," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662614.
- [111] M. Abid, P. Compagnon, and G. Lefebvre, "Improved CNN-based Magnetic Indoor Positioning System using Attention Mechanism," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662602.
- [112] L. Antsfeld and B. Chidlovskii, "Magnetic Field Sensing for Pedestrian and Robot Indoor Positioning," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662599.
- [113] D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, and J. Huerta, "Lightweight Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with a Novel RSS Clustering Algorithm," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662612.
- [114] G. G. Anagnostopoulos and A. Kalousis, "ProxyFAUG: Proximity-based Fingerprint Augmentation," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662590.
- [115] C. G. Pendão, I. Silva, A. J. C. Moreira, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "Dioptra - A Data Generation Application for Indoor Positioning Systems," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662612.

- Dec. 2, 2021, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662585.
- [116] S. Meyer *et al.*, “Contact Tracing with the Exposure Notification Framework in the German Corona-Warn-App,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662591.
- [117] G. Fischer *et al.*, “Localization of Acoustic Gas Leakage Sources with a Circular Microphone Array,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662589.
- [118] A. J. Martín, I. M. Gordo, J. J. G. Domínguez, J. Torres-Sospedra, S. L. Plaza, and D. G. Gómez, “Affinity Propagation Clustering for Older Adults Daily Routine Estimation,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662579.
- [119] H. Choi, T. Matsui, S. Misaki, A. Miyaji, M. Fujimoto, and K. Yasumoto, “Simultaneous Crowd Estimation in Counting and Localization Using WiFi CSI,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662572.
- [120] M. J. L. Lee, H. Y. Ho, L.-T. Hsu, and S. L. M. Au, “BIPS: Building Information Positioning System,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662575.
- [121] M. V. d. Wynckel and B. Signer, “Indoor Positioning Using the OpenHPS Framework,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662569.
- [122] K. Klipp, A. Kisand, J. Wortmann, and I. Radusch, “Multidimensional In- and Outdoor Pedestrian Tracking using OpenStreetMap Data,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662565.
- [123] F. J. Aranda, F. Parralejo, T. Aguilera, F. J. Alvarez, and J. Torres-Sospedra, “Finding Optimal BLE Configuration for Indoor Positioning with Consumption Restrictions,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662563.
- [124] I. Silva, C. G. Pendão, J. Torres-Sospedra, and A. J. C. Moreira, “Quantifying the Degradation of Radio Maps in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662558.
- [125] J. Macias-Sola, S. Uttendorf, and J. O. Blech, “A Ground Texture-based Mapping and Localization Method for AGVs,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662556.
- [126] E. Vertzberger and I. Klein, “Attitude and Heading Adaptive Estimation Using a Data Driven Approach,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662552.
- [127] Y. Wu, N. Joram, and R. T. Hach, “Quantitative Comparison of Distance Estimation Performance between TLS-MP and iFFT Methods in IEEE 802.15.4a Channel Models Using PSFM Radar Technique,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662549.
- [128] J. Barrows, V. Radu, M. Hill, and F. Ciravegna, “Active Learning with Data Distribution Shift Detection for Updating Localization Systems,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662543.
- [129] R. Klus, L. Klus, J. Talvitie, J. Pihlajasalo, J. Torres-Sospedra, and M. Valkama, “Transfer Learning for Convolutional Indoor Positioning Systems,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662544.
- [130] C. Rodríguez-Martínez and J. Torres-Sospedra, “Revisiting the Analysis of Hyperparameters in k-NN for Wi-Fi and BLE Fingerprinting: Current Status and General Results,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662542.
- [131] J. Friedrich, J. Tiemann, and C. Wietfeld, “Accurate Multi-Zone UWB TDOA Localization utilizing Cascaded Wireless Clock Synchronization,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662537.
- [132] L. Flueratoru, E. S. Lohan, and D. Niculescu, “Self-Learning Detection and Mitigation of Non-Line-of-Sight Measurements in Ultra-Wideband Localization,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662532.
- [133] C. Kjellson, M. Larsson, K. Åström, and M. Oskarsson, “Accurate Indoor Positioning Based on Learned Absolute and Relative Models,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662534.
- [134] S. Kaiser, Y. Wei, and V. Renaudin, “Analysis of IMU and GNSS Data Provided by Xiaomi 8 Smartphone,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662533.
- [135] Z. V. Hyfte and A. Zakhor, “Immediate Proximity Detection Using Wi-Fi-Enabled Smartphones,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662516.
- [136] N. A. Abiad, Y. Kone, V. Renaudin, and T. Robert, “SMARTphone inertial sensors based STEP detection driven by human gait learning,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662513.
- [137] M. Laska and J. Blankenbach, “Topology Preserving Input Image for Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662471.
- [138] C. D. Cock, W. Joseph, L. Martens, and D. Plets, “Floor Number Detection for Smartphone-based Pedestrian Dead Reckoning Applications,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662470.
- [139] S. Coene, C. D. Cock, E. Tanghe, D. Plets, L. Martens, and W. Joseph, “Using SAGE on COTS UWB Signals for TOA Estimation and Body Shadowing Effect Quantification,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662465.
- [140] H. Zeaiter, F. Spies, O. Baala, and T. Val, “SYLOIN: Measuring Angle of Arrival of LoRa signals using Software Defined Radio,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662518.
- [141] D. Kovalenko, A. Migukin, S. Ryabkova, and V. Chernov, “Pluto: Motion Detection for Navigation in a VR Headset,” in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662466.
- [142] J. A. López-Pastor, A. J. Ruiz-Ruiz, A. S. Martínez-Sala, and J. Luis Gómez-Tornero, “Evaluation of an indoor positioning system for added-value services in a mall,” in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911822.

- [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911822/>.
- [143] K.-J. Li, S. Zlatanova, J. Torres-Sospedra, A. Perez-Navarro, C. Laoudias, and A. Moreira, "Survey on Indoor Map Standards and Formats," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911796. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911796/>.
- [144] A. Bayev, I. Chistyakov, A. Derevyankin, I. Gartseev, A. Nikulin, and M. Pikhletsky, "RuDaCoP: The Dataset for Smartphone-based Intellectual Pedestrian Navigation," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911823. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911823/>.
- [145] J. Rojo *et al.*, "Machine Learning applied to Wi-Fi fingerprinting: The experiences of the Ubiquitous Challenge," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911761. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911761/>.
- [146] S. Prophet, J. Bao, and G. F. Trommer, "Comprehensive Floor Plan Mapping for Indoor Exploration and Guidance of Aerial Vehicles," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911807. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911807/>.
- [147] S. Khandker, R. Mondal, and T. Ristaniemi, "Positioning Error Prediction and Training Data Evaluation in RF Fingerprinting Method," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911821. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911821/>.
- [148] M. Lange, C. Raisch, and A. Schilling, "LVO: Line only stereo Visual Odometry," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911808. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911808/>.
- [149] J. Torres-Sospedra *et al.*, "Exploiting Different Combinations of Complementary Sensor's data for Fingerprint-based Indoor Positioning in Industrial Environments," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911758. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911758/>.
- [150] G. G. Anagnostopoulos and A. Kalousis, "A Reproducible Analysis of RSSI Fingerprinting for Outdoor Localization Using Sigfox: Preprocessing and Hyperparameter Tuning," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911792. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911792/>.
- [151] T. L. Koller and U. Frese, "State Observability through Prior Knowledge: Tracking Track Cyclers with Inertial Sensors," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911757. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911757/>.
- [152] G. Pipelidis *et al.*, "Cross-Device Radio Map Generation via Crowdsourcing," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911766. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911766/>.
- [153] B. Chidlovskii and L. Antsfeld, "Semi-supervised Variational Autoencoder for WiFi Indoor Localization," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911825. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911825/>.
- [154] R. Amsters, E. Demeester, P. Slaets, D. Holm, J. Joly, and N. Stevens, "Towards Automated Calibration of Visible Light Positioning Systems," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911756. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911756/>.
- [155] C. Li *et al.*, "CRLB-based Positioning Performance of Indoor Hybrid AoA/RSS/ToF Localization," in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2019.8911771. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8911771/>.
- [156] M. Angermann, P. Robertson, T. Kemptner, and M. Khider, "A high precision reference data set for pedestrian navigation using foot-mounted inertial sensors," in *2010 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation*, Sep. 2010, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2010.5646839.
- [157] H. Shoushtari, F. Kassawat, and H. Sternberg, "Context Aware Transformer Network and In-situ IMU Calibration For Accurate Positioning," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786130. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786130/>.
- [158] J. T. Zsolt Toth, *Miskolc IIS Hybrid IPS*, 2016. DOI: 10.24432/C5CS4R.
- [159] Z. Toth and J. Tamas, "Miskolc IIS hybrid IPS: Dataset for hybrid indoor positioning," en, in *2016 26th International Conference Radioelektronika (RADIOELEKTRONIKA)*, Kosice, Slovakia: IEEE, Apr. 2016, pp. 408–412. DOI: 10.1109/RADIOELEK.2016.7477348.
- [160] *Admtlab/retsina*, original-date: 2023-05-29T14:30:06Z, Jul. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/admtlab/retsina>.
- [161] G. M. Mendoza-Silva, P. Richter, J. Torres-Sospedra, E. S. Lohan, and J. Huerta, *Long-Term Wi-Fi fingerprinting dataset and supporting material*, Apr. 2020. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.1066040. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/1066040>.
- [162] G. M. Mendoza-Silva, P. Richter, J. Torres-Sospedra, E. S. Lohan, and J. Huerta, "Long-Term WiFi Fingerprinting Dataset for Research on Robust Indoor Positioning," en, *Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 3, Mar. 2018, Number: 1 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. DOI: 10.3390/data3010003.
- [163] D. V. Le and P. J. Havinga, "SoLoc: Self-organizing indoor localization for unstructured and dynamic environments," en, in *2017 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, Sapporo: IEEE, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN.2017.8115900.
- [164] Y. Cheng and R. Manduchi, "PALMS: Plane-based Accessible Indoor Localization Using Mobile Smartphones," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786167. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786167/>.
- [165] I. Skog, G. Hendeby, and F. Trullsson, "Magnetic-field Based Odometry - An Optical Flow Inspired Approach," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662626.
- [166] F. Parralejo, F. J. Aranda, J. A. Paredes, F. J. Alvarez, and J. Morera, "Comparative Study of Different BLE Fingerprint Reconstruction Techniques," in *International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021, Lloret de Mar, Spain, November 29 - Dec. 2, 2021*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN51156.2021.9662573.
- [167] Y. Dong, K. Kwan, and T. Arslan, "Enhanced Pedestrian Trajectory Reconstruction Using Bidirectional Extended Kalman Filter and Automatic Refinement," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786127. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786127/>.
- [168] M. Su, B. Wang, S. Ahad, X. Huang, G. Zhang, and L.-T. Hsu, "An Adaptive Weighted GNSS/VINS/Wi-Fi RTT-based Seamless Positioning System for Smartphone," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786175. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786175/>.
- [169] J. Grottko, D. Grottko, and J. Blankenbach, "Precise near-ultrasonic tilt determination for smartphones," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786184. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786184/>.

- [170] I. Vallivaara, Y. Dong, and T. Arslan, "Saying goodbyes to rotating your phone: Magnetometer calibration during SLAM," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786161. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786161/>.
- [171] L. Ju, H. Zhao, X. Ji, and D. Wei, "IBLI-SLAM: Intensity-Based LiDAR-Inertial SLAM for Dynamic Environments," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786137. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786137/>.
- [172] L. Wei, Z. Deng, B. Lou, and Y. Gao, "DSP-SLAM: A Robust Semantic Visual SLAM for Dynamic Environments," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786108. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786108/>.
- [173] N. Xiao *et al.*, "SUG-UAV Multirotor Dataset with Multi-sensor Integration in Indoor and Urban Areas," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786109. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786109/>.
- [174] M. J. L. Lee, J. Lin, and L.-T. Hsu, "Exploring the Feasibility of Automated Data Standardization using Large Language Models for Seamless Positioning," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786123. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786123/>.
- [175] G. G. Anagnostopoulos, "Efficient Fingerprint Augmentation Evaluation on the Antwerp LoRaWAN Setting," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786157. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786157/>.
- [176] Y. Zook, A. Shokry, and M. Youssef, "An Efficient Quantum Binary-Neuron Algorithm for Accurate Multi-Story Floor Localization," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786146. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786146/>.
- [177] C. De Cock, E. Tanghe, C. Marshall, N. Kouvelas, and D. Plets, "On the Feasibility of Phase-based BLE Ranging for Accurate Pedestrian Tracking," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786118. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786118/>.
- [178] C. Huang, G. Hendeby, and I. Skog, "An Observability-Constrained Magnetic Field-Aided Inertial Navigation System," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786170. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786170/>.
- [179] Z. Zhang *et al.*, "3D Indoor Localization via Universal Signal Fingerprinting Powered by LSTM," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786173. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786173/>.
- [180] F. Zha, "OPPCON: An Accurate, Efficient Algorithm for Dynamic Feature Extraction," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786140. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786140/>.
- [181] B. Han, T. Li, Z. Wang, and C. Shi, "Improving the performance of the ORB-SLAM3 with low-light image enhancement," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786104. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786104/>.
- [182] J. Ott, J. Pirkl, M. Stahlike, T. Feigl, and C. Mutschler, "Radio Foundation Models: Pre-training Transformers for 5G-based Indoor Localization," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786154. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786154/>.
- [183] H. Fu, V. Renaudin, T. Bonis, and N. Zhu, "MAPIN: Mobility Adapted Pedestrian Inertial Navigation Using Smartphones for Enhanced Travel of the Visually Impaired," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786129. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786129/>.
- [184] Z. Zhou *et al.*, "Data Collection and Alignment Algorithms for Data-driven Inertial Navigation," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786128. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786128/>.
- [185] G. L. D. Palma, A. Pérez-Navarro, and R. Montoliu, "Comparative Analysis of Pedestrian Dead Reckoning Algorithms for Indoor and Outdoor Localization," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786177. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786177/>.
- [186] M. Jan, W. Njima, and X. Zhang, "A Privacy-Preserving Indoor Localization System based on Hierarchical Federated Learning," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786152. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786152/>.
- [187] H. Hiruma, Y. Inoue, T. Sato, and H. Ohashi, "CSI-fingerprinting Based Human Indoor Localization in Noisy Environment using Time-Invariant CNN," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786163. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786163/>.
- [188] L. Hu, T. Wang, T. Niu, S. Yang, H. Ye, and Q. Zhang, "An Enhanced TDoA Method for 5G Real-Time Indoor Localization with Clustering," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786107. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786107/>.
- [189] A. Berg, J. Gulin, M. O'Connor, C. Zhou, K. Åström, and M. Oskarsson, "Wav2pos: Sound Source Localization using Masked Autoencoders," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786105. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786105/>.
- [190] D. Delabie, B. Cox, T. Feys, L. Van der Perre, and L. De Strycker, "Position Dependent Anchor Selection for Scalable Hybrid RF-Acoustic Indoor Positioning," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786115. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786115/>.
- [191] X. Li, H. Deng, J. Wang, L. Fu, and H. Kong, "Information-Aware Joint Calibration of Microphone Array and Sound Source Localization," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786166. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786166/>.
- [192] C. Gu, E. L. Grand, and M. Youssef, "Ubiquitous and Low-Cost Generation of Elevation Pseudo Ground Control Points," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786159. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786159/>.
- [193] J. Wortmann, B. Schäufele, K. Klipp, I. Radosch, K. Blaß, and T. Jung, "Enhanced Accessibility for Mobile Indoor Navigation," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786147. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786147/>.

- [194] Z. Huang, M. Valkama, J. Zhang, M. Xu, C. Yin, and M. Guan, "WiLoc: Encoding-based WiFi Indoor Localization," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786150. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786150/>.
- [195] T. Matsunaga, I. Arai, Y. Atarashi, A. Endo, and K. Fujikawa, "Performance Evaluation of Fingerprint-Based Indoor Positioning Using RSSI in 802.11ah," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786180. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786180/>.
- [196] N. Joswig, A. Morrison, N. Sokolova, and L. Ruotsalainen, "Plane Prior for RGB-D based Visual Odometry," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–8. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786120. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786120/>.
- [197] S. Kastner, M. Bullmann, M. Ebner, T. Fetzer, F. Deinzer, and M. Grzegorzec, "Refinement of Sparsely Tagged Ground Truth Paths Using PDR and Particle Filter Smoothing," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786186. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786186/>.
- [198] A. Diallo and B. Garbinato, "Drift Correction of Inertial Indoor Tracking using Peer Collaboration and Strategic Beacons Placement," in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, ISSN: 2471-917X, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/IPIN62893.2024.10786113. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10786113/>.

Grigorios G. Anagnostopoulos is a Research Associate at the Geneva School for Business Administration (HEG Geneva) of the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO), since 2018. He received his PhD in Information Systems, from the University of Geneva (UNIGE), Switzerland, in 2017. He has been a TPC member of the IPIN conference since 2021. Dr. Grigorios Anagnostopoulos has been an active advocate of Open and Reproducible science, operating as the local node

leader of the Swiss Reproducibility Network in his Institution (HES-SO). His research interests span Localization Systems, Sports Analytics, Open Science, and Research Reproducibility.

Paolo Barsocchi received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. in information engineering from the University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy, in 2003 and 2007, respectively. He is currently a researcher at the Information Science and Technologies Institute, National Research Council, Pisa. He has co-authored more than 150 articles published in international journals and conference proceedings. His research interests include IoT, cyber-physical systems, indoor localization, and radio channel signal processing. Dr. Barsocchi serves as associate

editor of the IEEE Journal of Indoor and Seamless Positioning and Navigation.

Antonino Crivello is a researcher at the Institute of Information Science and Technologies, National Research Council, Italy, since 2014. He received his PhD in Information Engineering and Science, University of Siena, in 2018. He is involved in the organization of IPIN competitions and is an associate editor of the IEEE Journal of Indoor and Seamless Positioning and Navigation. He also serves as associate editor of the Elsevier journal Expert Systems with Applications. He has been a TPC member of the IPIN conference since 2017. His research interests cover the Internet of Things, with a focus on interoperability, systems evaluation, open research data, and machine learning applied in different scenarios.

Cristiano Pendão is a Professor at the Department of Engineering, University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro, Portugal and he serves as Full Research Member of the ALGORITMI Research Centre, University of Minho. He received his Ph.D. in Telecommunications/Computer Science Engineering from the Universities of Minho, Aveiro, and Porto (2019). His research interests include mobile computing, positioning and navigation, computer vision/perception and machine learning. He has co-

authored several scientific publications and has actively participated in innovation and commercial projects within the industry.

Ivo Silva is a Professor at the Department of Information Systems, University of Minho and a Researcher at the Algoritmi Research Centre. He received his M.Sc. degree in Telecommunications and Informatics Engineering in 2016, followed by a Ph.D. degree in the MAP-tele Doctoral Program in Telecommunications from the Universities of Minho, Aveiro, and Porto in 2022. Ivo Silva has co-authored several scientific publications, and collaborated in R&D projects in partnership between academia and industry.

His research interests include Industry 4.0, indoor positioning and navigation, sensor fusion, vehicle localization, mobile computing, and Internet of Things.

Joaquín Torres-Sospedra is a Distinguished Researcher at Universitat de València (Burjassot, Spain). Funded by the program for the support of talented researchers (GenT Plan – Conselleria d'Educació, Universitats i Ocupació – Generalitat Valenciana – CIDEXG/2023/17), he works on Indoor Positioning and Machine Learning for Industrial applications. He has authored more than 180 articles in journals and conferences; and supervised 25 Master's and 7 PhD Students. He is the chair of the IPIN

International Standards Committee and IPIN Smartphone-based off-site Competition. He serves as Senior Editor of the Elsevier Journal Expert Systems with Applications.

TABLE I
LIST OF 150 PAPERS IDENTIFIED AS CONTAINING OPEN RESOURCES (CODE, DATA OR OTHER MATERIAL)

Paper's title	ORD	ORC	ORM	Year	Ref.
Enhanced Pedestrian Trajectory Reconstruction Using Bidirectional Extended Kalman Filter and Automatic Refinement	x	x	✓	2024	Dong <i>et al.</i> [167]
An Adaptive Weighted GNSS/VINS/Wi-Fi RTT-based Seamless Positioning System for Smartphone	x	x	✓	2024	Su <i>et al.</i> [168]
Precise near-ultrasonic tilt determination for smartphones	x	x	✓	2024	Grottko <i>et al.</i> [169]
Saying goodbyes to rotating your phone: Magnetometer calibration during SLAM	x	✓	✓	2024	Vallivara <i>et al.</i> [170]
IBLI-SLAM: Intensity-Based LiDAR-Inertial SLAM for Dynamic Environments	✓	x	x	2024	Ju <i>et al.</i> [171]
DSP-SLAM: A Robust Semantic Visual SLAM for Dynamic Environments	✓	x	x	2024	Wei <i>et al.</i> [172]
SUG-UAV Multirotor Dataset with Multi-sensor Integration in Indoor and Urban Areas	✓	x	x	2024	Xiao <i>et al.</i> [173]
Exploring the Feasibility of Automated Data Standardization using Large Language Models for Seamless Positioning	x	x	✓	2024	Lee <i>et al.</i> [174]
Evaluating Open Science Practices in Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation Research: A Survey of the IPIN's Reference Papers...	✓	x	x	2024	Anagnostopoulos <i>et al.</i> [16]
Efficient Fingerprint Augmentation Evaluation on the Antwerp LoRaWAN Setting	✓	✓	x	2024	Anagnostopoulos [175]
An Efficient Quantum Binary-Neuron Algorithm for Accurate Multi-Story Floor Localization	✓	x	x	2024	Zook <i>et al.</i> [176]
On the Feasibility of Phase-based BLE Ranging for Accurate Pedestrian Tracking	x	x	✓	2024	De Cock <i>et al.</i> [177]
An Observability-Constrained Magnetic Field-Aided Inertial Navigation System	x	✓	x	2024	Huang <i>et al.</i> [178]
3D Indoor Localization via Universal Signal Fingerprinting Powered by LSTM	x	x	✓	2024	Zhang <i>et al.</i> [179]
OPPCON: An Accurate, Efficient Algorithm for Dynamic Feature Extraction	✓	✓	x	2024	Zha [180]
Improving the performance of the ORB-SLAM3 with low-light image enhancement	✓	x	x	2024	Han <i>et al.</i> [181]
Radio Foundation Models: Pre-training Transformers for 5G-based Indoor Localization	x	x	✓	2024	Ott <i>et al.</i> [182]
MAPIN: Mobility Adapted Pedestrian Inertial Navigation Using Smartphones for Enhanced Travel of the Visually Impaired	x	x	✓	2024	Fu <i>et al.</i> [183]
Data Collection and Alignment Algorithms for Data-driven Inertial Navigation	x	x	✓	2024	Zhou <i>et al.</i> [184]
Comparative Analysis of Pedestrian Dead Reckoning Algorithms for Indoor and Outdoor Localization	x	x	✓	2024	Palma <i>et al.</i> [185]
A Privacy-Preserving Indoor Localization System based on Hierarchical Federated Learning	✓	x	x	2024	Jan <i>et al.</i> [186]
CSI-fingerprinting Based Human Indoor Localization in Noisy Environment using Time-Invariant CNN	x	x	✓	2024	Hiruma <i>et al.</i> [187]
An Enhanced TDoA Method for 5G Real-Time Indoor Localization with Clustering	✓	x	x	2024	Hu <i>et al.</i> [188]
wav2pos: Sound Source Localization using Masked Autoencoders	✓	✓	x	2024	Berg <i>et al.</i> [189]
Position Dependent Anchor Selection for Scalable Hybrid RF-Acoustic Indoor Positioning	x	x	✓	2024	Delabie <i>et al.</i> [190]
Information-Aware Joint Calibration of Microphone Array and Sound Source Localization	✓	✓	x	2024	Li <i>et al.</i> [191]
Context Aware Transformer Network and In-situ IMU Calibration For Accurate Positioning	✓	✓	x	2024	Shoushtari <i>et al.</i> [157]
Ubiquitous and Low-Cost Generation of Elevation Pseudo Ground Control Points	x	x	✓	2024	Gu <i>et al.</i> [192]
Enhanced Accessibility for Mobile Indoor Navigation	x	x	✓	2024	Wortmann <i>et al.</i> [193]
WiLoc: Encoding-based WiFi Indoor Localization	✓	x	x	2024	Huang <i>et al.</i> [194]
Performance Evaluation of Fingerprint-Based Indoor Positioning Using RSSI in 802.11ah	✓	x	✓	2024	Matsunaga <i>et al.</i> [195]
Plane Prior for RGB-D based Visual Odometry	✓	x	✓	2024	Joswig <i>et al.</i> [196]
Refinement of Sparsely Tagged Ground Truth Paths Using PDR and Particle Filter Smoothing	✓	x	✓	2024	Kastner <i>et al.</i> [197]
Drift Correction of Inertial Indoor Tracking using Peer Collaboration and Strategic Beacons Placement	✓	x	x	2024	Diallo <i>et al.</i> [198]
Millimetre Wave Radar System for Safe Flight of Drones in Human-Transited Environments	x	x	✓	2023	Parralajo <i>et al.</i> [41]
A Multimodal Graph Fingerprinting Method for Indoor Positioning Systems	x	x	✓	2023	Dong <i>et al.</i> [42]
FTM-Broadcast: Efficient Network-wide Ranging	x	✓	x	2023	Busnel <i>et al.</i> [43]
RETSINA: Reproducibility and Experimentation Testbed for Signal-Strength Indoor Near Analysis	✓	✓	✓	2023	Baskin <i>et al.</i> [44]
Close-Range Indoor Proximity Detection for COVID-19 Exposure Notifications Using Smartphone Magnetometer Traces	✓	x	✓	2023	Hyfte <i>et al.</i> [45]
SIMUL: Synchronized IMU Dataset of Walking People at Six Body Locations	✓	x	x	2023	Kastner <i>et al.</i> [46]
Simulation of machine learning inferences in real-time operating system to improve direction finding in an embedded environment	✓	✓	x	2023	Nizharadze <i>et al.</i> [47]
Deep Learning based Positioning with Beamformed CSI Fingerprints	x	x	✓	2023	Foliasidis <i>et al.</i> [48]
Magnetic Field-based Indoor Localization of a Tracked Robot with Simultaneous Calibration	x	x	✓	2023	Siebler <i>et al.</i> [49]
Step Length Is a More Reliable Measurement Than Walking Speed for Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning	x	✓	x	2023	Elyasi <i>et al.</i> [50]
Smartphone-Based Multi-Mode Geomagnetic Matching/PDR Integrated Indoor Positioning	x	x	✓	2023	Shao <i>et al.</i> [51]
Alternative Approach to Integrate GNSS Doppler in Kalman Filter for Smartphone Positioning	✓	x	x	2023	Agarwal <i>et al.</i> [52]
Error State Kalman Filter with Implicit Measurement Equations for Position Tracking of a Multi-Sensor System with IMU and LiDAR	✓	✓	x	2023	Ernst <i>et al.</i> [53]
Time-based vs. Fingerprinting-based Positioning Using Artificial Neural Networks	✓	x	x	2023	Kirmaz <i>et al.</i> [54]
Multipath Delay Estimation in Complex Environments using Transformer	✓	x	✓	2023	Ott <i>et al.</i> [55]
An empirical multi-wall NLOS ranging model for Wi-Fi RTT indoor positioning	✓	x	✓	2023	Liang <i>et al.</i> [56]
Towards Quality Wi-Fi Synthetic Data for Indoor Positioning Evaluation	✓	✓	x	2023	Pendão <i>et al.</i> [57]
Temporal Stability on Human Activity Recognition based on Wi-Fi CSI	✓	✓	x	2023	Matey-Sanz <i>et al.</i> [58]
RSS Channel-Based Integration for BLE Fingerprinting Positioning	✓	x	x	2023	Aranda <i>et al.</i> [59]
Towards Robust Visual Inertial Odometry in Feature Sparse Structured Environments	x	x	✓	2023	Joswig <i>et al.</i> [60]
Enhanced 5G Sidelink Ranging Based on Carrier Aggregation	x	x	✓	2023	Rasp <i>et al.</i> [61]
Overcoming Radio Map Degradation in Wi-Fi-based Positioning Systems	✓	✓	x	2023	Silva <i>et al.</i> [62]
Tightly Integrated Motion Classification and State Estimation in Foot-Mounted Navigation Systems	✓	✓	x	2023	Skog <i>et al.</i> [63]
Let's Talk about k-NN for Indoor Positioning: Myths and Facts in RF-based Fingerprinting	✓	✓	x	2023	Torres-Sospedra <i>et al.</i> [64]
Smartphone Indoor Positioning using Inertial and Ambient Light Sensors	x	x	✓	2023	Sugimoto <i>et al.</i> [65]
Cooperative Localization Using Received Signal Strength and Least Squares Estimation Methods	✓	x	x	2023	Moayeri [66]
Unsupervised Analysis of Daily Routine Evolution for Elderly People Using Room-Level Localisation	✓	x	x	2023	Plaza <i>et al.</i> [67]
A dynamic model switching algorithm for WiFi fingerprinting indoor positioning	✓	x	x	2023	Feng <i>et al.</i> [68]
Indoor Positioning Methods Based on Dual Feet-Mounted IMUs With Distance Constraints	✓	x	x	2023	Ma <i>et al.</i> [69]
UJI Probes: Dataset of Wi-Fi Probe Requests	✓	x	✓	2023	Bravenec <i>et al.</i> [70]
Pose Graph Optimization for a MAV Indoor Localization Fusing 5GNR TOA with an IMU	✓	x	✓	2023	Kabiri <i>et al.</i> [71]
VI-SLAM2tag: Low-Effort Labeled Dataset Collection for Fingerprinting-Based Indoor Localization	✓	✓	✓	2022	Laska <i>et al.</i> [72]
SURIMI: Supervised Radio Map Augmentation with Deep Learning and a Generative Adversarial Network for Fingerprint-based Indoor Positioning	✓	✓	✓	2022	Quezada-Gaibor <i>et al.</i> [73]
IMU-aided detection and mitigation of Human Body Shadowing for UWB positioning	x	x	✓	2022	Cock <i>et al.</i> [74]
Live RSSI Filtering for Indoor Positioning with Bluetooth Low-Energy	✓	x	x	2022	Danis [75]
A Survey on Artificial Intelligence for Pedestrian Navigation with Wearable Inertial Sensors	✓	x	✓	2022	Fu <i>et al.</i> [76]
What Your Wearable Devices Revealed About You and Possibilities of Non-Cooperative 802.11 Presence Detection During Your Last IPIN Visit	x	x	✓	2022	Bravenec <i>et al.</i> [77]
ONavi: Data-driven based Multi-sensor Fusion Positioning System in Indoor Environments	✓	✓	x	2022	Lu <i>et al.</i> [78]
WiFi Based Distance Estimation Using Supervised Machine Learning	✓	x	x	2022	Kostas <i>et al.</i> [79]
Online IMU-Odometer Extrinsic Calibration Based on Visual-Inertial-Odometer Fusion for Ground Vehicles	✓	✓	✓	2022	Zhao <i>et al.</i> [80]
Beacon Placement and Signal Strength Estimation to Improve Localization Coverage and Accuracy	x	x	✓	2022	Uphayay <i>et al.</i> [81]
An Enhanced Visual SLAM Supported by the Integration of Plane Features for the Indoor Environment	✓	x	x	2022	Zi <i>et al.</i> [82]
The Semantic Point & Line SLAM for Indoor Dynamic Environment	✓	x	✓	2022	Guo <i>et al.</i> [83]
Multi-Head Attention Neural Network for Smartphone Invariant Indoor Localization	x	x	✓	2022	Tiku <i>et al.</i> [84]
A Geometric Deep Learning Framework for Accurate Indoor Localization	✓	x	x	2022	Luo <i>et al.</i> [85]
A WiFi Fingerprint Augmentation Method for 3-D Crowdsourced Indoor Positioning Systems	✓	x	x	2022	Dong <i>et al.</i> [86]
An Encoded LSTM Network Model for WiFi-based Indoor Positioning	✓	x	x	2022	Dong <i>et al.</i> [87]
A Framework for CSI-Based Indoor Localization with ID Convolutional Neural Networks	✓	x	x	2022	Wang <i>et al.</i> [88]
Data Driven Sensor Model for Wi-Fi Fine Timing Measurement	x	x	✓	2022	Bullmann <i>et al.</i> [89]
PnPloc: UWB Based Plug & Play Indoor Localization	x	x	✓	2022	Chen <i>et al.</i> [90]
Measuring accurate Angle of Arrival of weak LoRa signals for Indoor Positioning	x	x	✓	2022	Zeaier <i>et al.</i> [91]
Unscented Kalman Filtering Based Multipath-assisted Positioning with Peak Flow Tracking	x	x	✓	2022	Xu <i>et al.</i> [92]
Smartphone-based WiFi FTM Fingerprinting Approach with Map-aided Particle Filter	x	x	✓	2022	Sun <i>et al.</i> [93]
An IoT Based Approach for Platform Independent Positioning Service	x	x	✓	2022	Vu <i>et al.</i> [94]
PIPF: Proposal-Interpolating Particle Filter	x	x	✓	2022	Ebner <i>et al.</i> [95]
OW-LOAM: Observation-Weighted LiDAR Odometry and Mapping	x	✓	x	2022	Zhang <i>et al.</i> [96]
A Metric for Quantifying UWB Ranging Error Due to Clock Drifts	x	x	✓	2022	Chen <i>et al.</i> [97]
Decision Trees for Analyzing Influences on the Accuracy of Indoor Localization Systems	x	x	✓	2022	Schyga <i>et al.</i> [98]
Online Magnetometer Calibration in Indoor Environments for Magnetic field-based SLAM	x	x	✓	2022	Coulin <i>et al.</i> [99]

TABLE II
LIST OF 150 PAPERS ANALYZED (CONTINUATION)

Paper's title	Data	Code	Mat.	Year	Ref.
Completely Automated CNN Architecture Design Based on VGG Blocks for Fingerprinting Localisation	✓	✗	✗	2021	Sinha <i>et al.</i> [100]
DL-AOD Positioning Algorithm for Enhanced 5G NR Location Services	✗	✗	✓	2021	Sosnin <i>et al.</i> [101]
Design of an RFID-based positioning system for safety of personnel in nuclear facilities	✗	✗	✓	2021	Tormo <i>et al.</i> [102]
3D Indoor Localization using 5G-based Particle Filtering and CAD Plans	✓	✗	✗	2021	Shoushtari <i>et al.</i> [103]
Comparing and Evaluating Indoor Positioning Techniques	✓	✓	✓	2021	Raza <i>et al.</i> [104]
CovTracer-EN: The Journey of Covid-19 Digital Contact Tracing in Cyprus	✗	✓	✓	2021	Isaia <i>et al.</i> [105]
Combined ADS-B and GNSS Indoor Localization	✗	✗	✓	2021	Josephy <i>et al.</i> [106]
An End-to-end Beacon Placement Optimization System for Indoor Positioning	✗	✗	✓	2021	Zhang <i>et al.</i> [107]
RAD-GAN: Radio Map Anomaly Detection for Fingerprint Indoor Positioning with GAN	✓	✗	✗	2021	Ai <i>et al.</i> [108]
Robust ToA-Estimation using Convolutional Neural Networks on Randomized Channel Models	✗	✗	✓	2021	Feigl <i>et al.</i> [109]
YO-VIO: Robust Multi-Sensor Semantic Fusion Localization in Dynamic Indoor Environments	✓	✓	✓	2021	Huang <i>et al.</i> [110]
Improved CNN-based Magnetic Indoor Positioning System using Attention Mechanism	✓	✗	✗	2021	Abid <i>et al.</i> [111]
Magnetic Field Sensing for Pedestrian and Robot Indoor Positioning	✓	✗	✗	2021	Antsfeld <i>et al.</i> [112]
Lightweight Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with a Novel RSS Clustering Algorithm	✓	✗	✗	2021	Quezada-Gaibor <i>et al.</i> [113]
ProxyFAUG: Proximity-based Fingerprint Augmentation	✓	✓	✗	2021	Anagnostopoulos <i>et al.</i> [114]
Dioptra - A Data Generation Application for Indoor Positioning Systems	✗	✗	✓	2021	Pendão <i>et al.</i> [115]
Contact Tracing with the Exposure Notification Framework in the German Corona-Warn-App	✗	✗	✓	2021	Meyer <i>et al.</i> [116]
Localization of Acoustic Gas Leakage Sources with a Circular Microphone Array	✗	✗	✓	2021	Fischer <i>et al.</i> [117]
Affinity Propagation Clustering for Older Adults Daily Routine Estimation	✗	✗	✓	2021	Martín <i>et al.</i> [118]
Simultaneous Crowd Estimation in Counting and Localization Using WiFi CSI	✗	✗	✓	2021	Choi <i>et al.</i> [119]
BIPS: Building Information Positioning System	✗	✗	✓	2021	Lee <i>et al.</i> [120]
Indoor Positioning Using the OpenHPS Framework	✓	✓	✓	2021	Wynckel <i>et al.</i> [121]
Multidimensional In- and Outdoor Pedestrian Tracking using OpenStreetMap Data	✗	✗	✓	2021	Klipp <i>et al.</i> [122]
Finding Optimal BLE Configuration for Indoor Positioning with Consumption Restrictions	✓	✗	✗	2021	Aranda <i>et al.</i> [123]
Towards Ubiquitous Indoor Positioning: Comparing Systems across Heterogeneous Datasets	✓	✗	✗	2021	Torres-Sospedra <i>et al.</i> [35]
Quantifying the Degradation of Radio Maps in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	✓	✗	✗	2021	Silva <i>et al.</i> [124]
A Ground Texture-based Mapping and Localization Method for AGVs	✗	✗	✓	2021	Macias-Sola <i>et al.</i> [125]
Attitude and Heading Adaptive Estimation Using a Data Driven Approach	✓	✗	✗	2021	Vertzberger <i>et al.</i> [126]
Quantitative Comparison of Distance Estimation Performance between TLS-MP and iFFT Methods in ...	✗	✓	✓	2021	Wu <i>et al.</i> [127]
Active Learning with Data Distribution Shift Detection for Updating Localization Systems	✓	✗	✗	2021	Barrows <i>et al.</i> [128]
Transfer Learning for Convolutional Indoor Positioning Systems	✓	✗	✗	2021	Klus <i>et al.</i> [129]
Revisiting the Analysis of Hyperparameters in k-NN for Wi-Fi and BLE Fingerprinting: Current Status and General Results	✓	✗	✗	2021	Rodríguez-Martínez <i>et al.</i> [130]
Accurate Multi-Zone UWB TDOA Localization utilizing Cascaded Wireless Clock Synchronization	✓	✓	✗	2021	Friedrich <i>et al.</i> [131]
Self-Learning Detection and Mitigation of Non-Line-of-Sight Measurements in Ultra-Wideband Localization	✓	✗	✗	2021	Flueratoru <i>et al.</i> [132]
Accurate Indoor Positioning Based on Learned Absolute and Relative Models	✓	✗	✗	2021	Kjellson <i>et al.</i> [133]
Analysis of IMU and GNSS Data Provided by Xiaomi 8 Smartphone	✗	✗	✓	2021	Kaiser <i>et al.</i> [134]
Immediate Proximity Detection Using Wi-Fi-Enabled Smartphones	✓	✗	✗	2021	Hyfte <i>et al.</i> [135]
SMARTphone inertial sensors based STEP detection driven by human gait learning	✗	✗	✓	2021	Abiad <i>et al.</i> [136]
Topology Preserving Input Image for Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization	✓	✗	✗	2021	Laska <i>et al.</i> [137]
Floor Number Detection for Smartphone-based Pedestrian Dead Reckoning Applications	✗	✗	✓	2021	Cock <i>et al.</i> [138]
Using SAGE on COTS UWB Signals for TOA Estimation and Body Shadowing Effect Quantification	✗	✗	✓	2021	Coene <i>et al.</i> [139]
SYLOIN: Measuring Angle of Arrival of LoRa signals using Software Defined Radio	✗	✗	✓	2021	Zeiter <i>et al.</i> [140]
Pluto: Motion Detection for Navigation in a VR Headset	✓	✗	✗	2021	Kovalenko <i>et al.</i> [141]
Evaluation of an indoor positioning system for added-value services in a mall	✗	✗	✓	2019	López-Pastor <i>et al.</i> [142]
Survey on Indoor Map Standards and Formats	✗	✗	✓	2019	Li <i>et al.</i> [143]
RuDaCoP: The Dataset for Smartphone-based Intellectual Pedestrian Navigation	✓	✗	✗	2019	Bayev <i>et al.</i> [144]
Machine Learning applied to Wi-Fi fingerprinting: The experiences of the Ubiquitous Challenge	✓	✗	✗	2019	Rojo <i>et al.</i> [145]
Comprehensive Floor Plan Mapping for Indoor Exploration and Guidance of Aerial Vehicles	✗	✓	✗	2019	Prophet <i>et al.</i> [146]
Positioning Error Prediction and Training Data Evaluation in RF Fingerprinting Method	✓	✗	✗	2019	Khandker <i>et al.</i> [147]
LVO: Line only stereo Visual Odometry	✓	✗	✓	2019	Lange <i>et al.</i> [148]
Exploiting Different Combinations of Complementary Sensor's data for Fingerprint-based Indoor Positioning in Industrial Environments	✓	✗	✓	2019	Torres-Sospedra <i>et al.</i> [149]
A Reproducible Analysis of RSSI Fingerprinting for Outdoor Localization Using Sigfox: Preprocessing and Hyperparameter Tuning	✓	✓	✗	2019	Anagnostopoulos <i>et al.</i> [150]
State Observability through Prior Knowledge: Tracking Track Cyclers with Inertial Sensors	✓	✓	✗	2019	Koller <i>et al.</i> [151]
Cross-Device Radio Map Generation via Crowdsourcing	✓	✗	✗	2019	Pipelidis <i>et al.</i> [152]
Semi-supervised Variational Autoencoder for WiFi Indoor Localization	✓	✗	✗	2019	Chidlovskii <i>et al.</i> [153]
Towards Automated Calibration of Visible Light Positioning Systems	✗	✗	✓	2019	Amsters <i>et al.</i> [154]
CRLB-based Positioning Performance of Indoor Hybrid AoA/RSS/ToF Localization	✗	✗	✓	2019	Li <i>et al.</i> [155]